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EQUALITY SURVEY 2018

WHITE PAPER

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LETTER FROM THE 1ST VICE PRESIDENT

In universities of Science and Technology (S&T), the greatest potential to boost research, education and innovation lies in promoting excellent researchers. Promoting excellence in research starts with studies and academic career paths that are attractive and achievable for all talent irrespective of gender, origin, (dis-) ability, age or family responsibilities. Only in an inclusive environment characterised by equal opportunity, universities of S&T are recognised as attractive employers capable of recruiting, motivating and retaining the best talent. However, inequality - particularly concerning women - remains a long-standing challenge.

This white paper aims to provide grounds for discussion and present potential tools to help S&T universities in the process of creating, or refining pre-existing, organisational cultures, structures and targeted effort which helps ensure equal access and participation. It captures the *status quo* and benchmarks the progress of gender equality and diversity at our Member institutions. It can serve as a means for exchange of experiences and lessons learned and it formulates recommendations for Human Resources (HR) professionals and change agents, university leaders as well as policymakers in an effort to strengthen existing equality initiatives and form the basis for the advancement of gender equality, diversity and inclusion at universities of S&T. It also forms part of the implementation of our commitments to the European Research Area (ERA) partnership.

The statements and recommendations in this paper are based on the findings of the Equality Survey 2018, which collected a second round of data to follow up on our [Gender Equality Survey 2014](#). The 2018 survey re-framed the earlier context to include an additional section on diversity. This white paper presents a wealth of activities and a broad spectrum of target dimensions, strategic Gender Equality Plans (GEP) and Diversity Plans (DP) at universities of S&T. It shows that good approaches do exist by listing numerous [best practice](#) examples from our Member institutions. However, they are not sufficient to ensure equal participation. The aim is to make HR professionals and change agents aware of the continued importance of gender and diversity management within a comprehensive change management process towards a culture of inclusion for all. Strong and continued engagement at all levels is needed to seize the momentum of change. It is therefore essential to recognise and stress the importance of our role as trainers for the leaders of tomorrow and it is my firm belief that if we master this challenge change will be possible for society as a whole. University leaders guided by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals ([UN SDG](#)) must push their organisations to become role models and yardsticks for benchmarking.

I thank the Integration Team - Human Resources, Gender and Diversity Management (IGaD) and Doris Klee (Vice-Rector for Human Resources Management and Development at RWTH Aachen University and Chair of our Task Force Human Resources) for developing and executing the Equality Survey 2018 and for compiling this white paper with dedication and expertise.

Sigbritt Karlsson
Vice President Leadership & Sustainability
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This white paper records the current status of gender equality and diversity at universities of S&T and reports and clarifies recommendations for HR professionals and change agents, university leaders as well as national and international policymakers in order to further promote gender equality and diversity, so that access to and participation in S&T will become possible for all irrespective of their background. The statements and recommendations are based on the findings of the second Equality Survey 2018 among our Members.

It presents structures, policies, measures and target dimensions of gender equality and diversity at 31 participating Members in [chapter 2](#). In [chapter 3](#), we outline best practice examples, future plans to increase equality, internal and external push and pull-factors supporting equality as well as challenges and resistances faced when setting up equality measures. In [chapter 4](#), statistical data is presented and analysed. The evaluation includes gender equality data on academic and administrative top management, students and graduates, scientific staff, appointment committees as well as Horizon 2020 grants and projects. In [chapter 5](#), we compare the results of chapters 2, 3 and 4 with the findings of the first Gender Equality Survey 2014 including gender equality strategy papers, activities, best practices, barriers and statistical data. We draw conclusions and formulate recommendations for HR professionals, change agents, university leaders and policymakers in [chapter 6](#).

The paper presents a myriad of activities and sustained efforts accompanied by a broad set of targets and strategy papers at universities of S&T aiming at equal participation in science and research. Nevertheless, the change momentum, especially in gender equality, is slow, and the paper demonstrates that the science system is leaking and losing most of its female talents along the academic career path. We report slight changes in the proportion of women in the higher ranks of the academic career illustrating that efforts targeted towards female professors are not in vain. However, persistent commitment and further measures are needed. The situation is even more challenging due to the stagnant development of female students in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). The comparison of data from 2014 and 2018 reveals almost no change in STEM study subjects.

HR professionals and change agents have to further push successful existing measures and develop new initiatives that enable and motivate a diverse population of talented individuals, especially women, to enter studies and to pursue an academic career in STEM. Furthermore, qualified and motivated researchers from underrepresented groups have to be supported in attaining leadership positions in academia. This paper presents numerous best practices from which to draw inspiration from. University leaders have to initiate top-down impetus for change by simultaneously allowing for bottom-up participation of all university members. Awareness of equality issues and a sensitive mind-set have to be lived by all university members in all parts of the organisation. Therefore, university leaders have to take on responsibility for the process, create appropriate organisational structures and strategies and equip the players with sufficient resources. Universities of S&T have to give significant impetus and collaborate with civic partners and education institutions by setting up joint measures and programmes. Finally, to promote a strategic perspective on equality at universities of S&T, national and international policymakers are called to follow the development of a broader perspective on equal opportunities by nurturing diversity projects through research funding and creating the legal and political framework conditions for increased speed of change.

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1 INTRODUCTION

With gender equality, we refer to “equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities of women and men and girls and boys [...] seen both as a human rights issue and as a precondition for, and indicator of, sustainable people-centred development” (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2019). In this context the term “gender” is not to be equated with biological sex, but rather “social attributes and opportunities associated with being male and female [...] [which are] socially constructed and [...] learned through socialisation processes” (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2019). Due to persisting underrepresentation of women in science and research, promoting gender equality in this paper implies promoting women in academia at universities of S&T. Talking about diversity, we acknowledge interpersonal differences with regards to “origin and culture, age, gender and gender identity, sexual orientation and identity, religious beliefs and worldviews and our physical and mental abilities” (*Charta der Vielfalt e. V.*, 2019).

In this paper, diversity management not only means acknowledging differences. It implies a strategic approach “to include and value each employee equally on the basis of their diverse characteristics, and to leverage organisational diversity to enhance organisational justice and achieve better [research] outcomes” (Groutsis, Ng and Ozturk, 2014). Here, equality unites gender equality, diversity and inclusion and encompasses equal opportunities, treatment and participation for everyone regardless of their gender and/or background.

The statements and recommendations to establish equality are based on the evaluation of data collected in the framework of the Equality Survey 2018. The survey has been conducted and analysed by the Integration Team – Human Resources, Gender and Diversity Management (IGaD) at RWTH Aachen University in collaboration with the Task Force Human Resources. It was distributed among the 52 Members in spring 2018 via an online questionnaire. The questions were practice-oriented with the aim to enable universities of S&T to monitor their activities, to benchmark their progress and to formulate concrete recommendations. By the end of autumn 2018, data collection was closed so that the evaluation of the survey results started with the fall of winter 2018. Following the Gender Equality Survey 2014, it forms the second data collection round. Both surveys are similar in structure and content, whereas the survey of 2018 is the first to take into account diversity activities and target dimensions. For both subject fields, the survey delivered interesting insights such as high-quality strategy papers and comprehensive answers in free text fields.

The Equality Survey 2018 was structured into five parts:

1. Identification of respondent;
2. Structures and measures supporting diversity;
3. Structures and measures supporting gender equality;
4. Strategies, best practices, barriers, tools and resources;
5. Quantitative data 2017.

PART I to III mostly contained single-choice and multiple-choice items. PART IV consisted of mostly free-text fields and one multiple-choice question. PART V asked for figures and numbers ranging from academic and administrative top-management, scientific staff at different levels, students and graduates as well as Horizon 2020 grants. For all of these items absolute numbers were requested, including the total number as well as the number of women for the respective category. With 31 of 52 Members participating in the survey, the response rate was at approximately 60%.

This white paper follows the structure of the Equality Survey 2018. First, it presents structures, policies and measures supporting gender equality and diversity ([chapter 2](#)). Due to the similarity of the survey questions in PART II and III responsibilities and structures as well as strategies and policies are outlined for both fields of action. In [chapter 3](#), we outline best practice examples at our Members - of which selected ones can be found throughout the paper - and future steps to increase equality give an insight into the way forward. Furthermore, we present internal and external push and pull-factors supporting equality as well as challenges and resistances faced when setting up measures. In the [chapter 4](#), statistical data for 2017 (PART V) is analysed and compared, where possible, to EU-28 figures reported by the [She Figures 2018](#) and other European publications. In [chapter 5](#), we compare the data of the Equality Survey 2018 with the Gender Equality Survey 2014. Finally, [chapter 6](#) concludes the white paper and formulates recommendations for different stakeholders based on the findings of the preceding chapters.

There are several methodological and content-related limitations of this paper. Methodological limitations concern the comparative perspective of the Equality Survey 2018 results with figures at EU-28 level and associated countries concerning the representativeness of the survey sample as well as cross-country comparability of figures. Furthermore, comparing results from the Gender Equality Survey 2014 and the Equality Survey 2018 is constrained by the differing sample of universities of S&T, partly different survey questions, requested data formats and reference periods. Content-related constraints affect the interpretation of survey results across different countries. In this paper, we have refrained from analysing social, legal and political framework conditions per country. This would exceed the scope of this paper, and therefore, we can only draw conditional conclusions regarding environmental push and pull factors that influence the direction and maturity of equality measures at universities of S&T in different countries.

2 STRUCTURES, POLICIES AND MEASURES SUPPORTING EQUALITY

In this chapter, we present the results regarding structures and measures that support diversity and gender equality within Member institutions. The survey questionnaire systematically asked for structural and strategic anchoring of equal opportunities and contents and implementation of the strategies.

In the first two sub-chapters, we integrate the survey results of Part II and III. This means that we present responsibilities and structures as well as strategies and policies for both: diversity and gender equality. The aim is to synthesise the results and to avoid redundancies, which might occur due to the similarity of the survey questions.

2.1 RESPONSIBILITIES AND STRUCTURES

This chapter summarises the structural embedding of diversity and gender equality within our Member institutions. The survey contained two identical questions, whereas the question on diversity listed an additional item (separate unit for each diversity dimension). Multiple answers were possible. Concurrent with the questionnaire structure, the following chart presents results on diversity followed by gender equality.

Figure 1: Comparison of responsibilities and structures in gender equality and diversity

The survey evaluation shows that diversity is most likely embedded at the level of **rector, board member or equivalent** followed by a **separate unit for each diversity dimension**. Further diversity is embedded through **commissions, special organisational units, deans/faculties as well as units with broader responsibilities**. The items a **single person for this topic external advisory group** as well as a **single person with multiple responsibilities** received little to no attention. Three respondents had no structural embedding for diversity. Evidently, diversity is most commonly embedded at top organisational level of the university such as rectorate, deanships and special organisational units for diversity as well as for each diversity dimension.

All 31 participants replied to this question naming three organisational structures on average. Four universities had more than five structural anchors (two universities named six). Six respondents named only one structure for diversity with no common pattern of its organisational location. This underpins the importance of diversity management at our Members.

As shown in Figure 1, gender equality was most likely embedded at the level of **rector, board members or equivalent, deans/faculties, through special organisational units and commissions**. Approximately one-third of the universities had a unit in charge of gender equality among other responsibilities. Gender equality was rarely embedded through a **single person with multiple responsibilities**, an **external advisory group** nor a **single person** in charge of gender equality only. Only one respondent had no structural embedding for gender equality. As for diversity, responsibilities for gender equality are most likely assigned at the top organisational level e.g. in the rectorate, deanships, commissions and special organisational units for gender equality. Regarding the distribution of measures across participating institutions, the picture is quite similar to diversity outlined in the preceding paragraph: the respondents named three organisational structures on average, whereas four of them had five organisational structures in place. Four - slightly less than for diversity - universities had only one structural anchoring of gender equality allocated at lower levels of the organisational hierarchy e.g. one single person is dealing with gender equality among other responsibilities. As for diversity, the results show that gender equality management is even more prominent on the agenda of our Members: no participant had no structural anchoring and only four had only one organisational structure.

In summary, both gender equality and diversity seem to be well established topics allocated at high levels of the organisational structure at our Members. When reviewing the surveys one noticeable finding was that those institutions with rectorate responsibility assigned for diversity (18) always have rectorate responsibility for gender equality, i.e. not all universities with rectorate responsibility for gender equality have rectorate responsibility for diversity. No institution exclusively has diversity responsibility allocated at the leadership level (without gender equality). The same applies to the level of deans and illustrates that diversity and even more gender equality are also on the agenda of decentralised leadership. From this sample, we can hypothesise that gender equality leadership commitment always takes precedence over diversity leadership commitment.

Moreover, the analysis yields insights into leadership responsibility and its underpinning by the organisational structures. For both diversity and gender equality, leadership responsibility does not automatically determine the existence of a special organisational unit and organisational anchoring of gender equality seems to be more common than for diversity. Eight respondents who have diversity responsibilities assigned at rectorate level have a special organisational unit in place; 15 institutions with gender equality responsibility at the rectorate also have a special organisation unit.

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 1

TU Wien - Target agreements with deans/faculties

The rectorate concludes three annual target agreements with each of the eight faculties. Among other things, (quantitative and qualitative) gender objectives are defined in the target agreements: the overall aim is to increase the proportion of women at all levels by effective measures. Examples of measures, which are proposed by the faculties themselves, include identifying specific vacancies or grants for which only women can apply; improving the compatibility of family and work or inviting as many women as men to congresses and workshops. Target agreements are evaluated on a yearly basis, the whole team of the rectorate is involved in this process.

Not publicly available

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 2

RWTH Aachen University - forumDiversity

The forumDIVERSITY has been established as a central advisory board for shaping the Diversity Policy at RWTH Aachen University. It is hosted by the rectorate staff unit for gender and diversity management. The aim is to inform and reflect about the development of an open and inclusive university. Therefore, forumDIVERSITY focuses on opening the university (educational equality, equitable access and broader social participation), initiating cultural change (appreciation of diversity, equal study and career paths), designing a life-phase-oriented staff policy (consideration of diverse life plans as well as inclusion of individual qualification phases) and strengthening of gender and diversity skills (diversity-sensitive leadership and non-discriminatory interaction) in line with the university's strategic objectives.

<http://www.igad.rwth-aachen.de/>

2.2 STRATEGIES AND POLICIES

The following table lists all 31 participating Member institutions. They are organised and clustered according to the prevalence of GEP and DP. Furthermore, the table shows for which universities gender equality and diversity are an integrated part of the university strategy and which universities plan to develop GEP and DP. The fields highlighted in grey indicate which universities evaluate the implementation of their plans.

Table 1: Gender Equality and Diversity Plans at Members institutions

UNIVERSITIES	CITY	COUNTRY	GENDER EQUALITY PLAN (GEP)	DIVERSITY PLAN (DP)	NO SEPARATE GEP OR DP, BUT	
					INTEGRATED IN UNIVERSITY STRATEGY	PLAN IN DEVELOPMENT
UNIVERSITIES WITH GEP AND DP						
TU Graz	Graz	AT	•	•		
TU Wien	Vienna	AT	•	•		
Ghent University	Ghent	BE	•	•		
KU Leuven	Leuven	BE	•	•		
EPFL	Lausanne	CH	•	•		
LUH	Hannover	DE	•	•		
RWTH	Aachen	DE	•	•		
UPC	Barcelona	ES	•	•		
Aalto University	Aalto	FI	•	•		
INSA Lyon	Lyon	FR	•	•	DP	
UCD	Dublin	IE	•	•		
Polimi	Milan	IT	•	•		
NTNU	Trondheim	NO	•	•		
Chalmers	Gothenburg	SE	•	•		
KTH	Stockholm	SE	•	•		
Strathclyde	Glasgow	UK	•	•		
UNIVERSITIES WITH GEP OR DP						
ETH Zurich	Zurich	CH	•		DP	
TU Berlin	Berlin	DE	•			DP
TU Braunschweig	Braunschweig	DE	•			DP
TU Darmstadt	Darmstadt	DE	•		DP	DP
KIT	Karlsruhe	DE	•		DP	DP
UPM	Madrid	ES	•			GEP & DP
UPV	Valencia	ES	•			GEP & DP
TU Delft	Delft	NL		•	GEP	GEP
UNIVERSITIES WITHOUT PLANS						
TalTech	Tallinn	EE			GEP	DP
BME	Budapest	HU			GEP & DP	
PoliTo	Turin	IT				GEP & DP
KTU	Kaunas	LT				GEP & DP
RTU	Riga	LV				GEP & DP
PUT	Poznan	PL			GEP & DP	
WUT	Warsaw	PL			GEP & DP	
TOTAL			23	17	9	11

More than half of the respondents indicated that they have a GEP and a DP in place. Evidently, most of the members of this group stem from long-term EU member states (EU accession in or before 1995), e.g. Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Spain, Sweden (European Commission, 2015).

The second group of universities have either a GEP or a DP. Evidently, half of the participants in this group are German institutions – all of them possessing a GEP and no DP, but planning to develop DP in the future. Interestingly TU Delft was the only participant with a DP but no GEP. The third group is composed of institutions that indicated that they neither have a GEP nor a DP but had plans to develop either one of them or both. In this group, the minority of institutions (two out of seven) did have gender equality and diversity embedded at the top university leadership level. Furthermore, over half of the seven universities in this group indicated that they had no special organisational unit established, but a single person was responsible for gender equality or diversity among other duties. Consequently, we can state that leadership awareness and commitment are strong drivers in the development and implementation of strategy papers for gender equality and diversity. Furthermore, most of the members of this group stem from EU member states that joined in the 2004 enlargement round or later (European Commission, 2015). The differing results per EU member states might be due to varying legal and cultural framework conditions in the respective countries. As this would exceed the scope of this paper, we are refraining from going into detail regarding individual conditions per country.

Another hypothesis is that those universities with anchoring at the rectorate level have consistently backed it with strategies. We found that this is partially the case in our sample of universities of S&T.

In summary, all 31 participating universities either have GEP and DP, have plans to develop these or have the topics enshrined in their university strategy. Moreover, the existing plans are almost always accompanied by the evaluation of their implementation. This underlines once again the importance and sensitivity of both topics. The next page gives best practice examples of a GEP and a DP or equality plan.

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 3

University of Strathclyde - Gender Action Plan (GAP)

“While concerns about gender imbalances at subject level have often focused on the lower proportion of women in STEM, we recognise that addressing gender imbalances and occupational segregation also requires a focus on male subject choices, attainment and occupational decisions. This includes increasing male participation in, for example, Education and European Languages, Literature and related subjects. [...] we have engaged schools and departments within our Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences and our Business School in the scheme, with all departments now on a timeline to submit for awards. This includes the development of actions to increase the proportion of either female or male students where a gender imbalance has been identified. [...]

The following Gender Action Plan (GAP) incorporates ongoing and planned student gender equality actions, grouped across the five themes of Infrastructure; Influencing the Influencers; Raising awareness and aspiration; Encouraging applications; and Supporting Success.”

https://www.strath.ac.uk/media/ps/sees/equality/Gender_Action_Plan.pdf

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 4

Aalto University - Equality Plan

“The Aalto University Equality Plan 2016–2018 applies to all who work and study at Aalto. Every member of the university community has a responsibility to promote equality where they are, in their own environment. Key to the promotion of equality are also the management teams of the university and the schools and the directors of the departments, units and services. [...]

Aalto University aims to provide a non-discriminatory, gender-equal and accessible environment [...] in which all genders, employees with different duties, and employees and students of different backgrounds receive equal treatment and can participate without discrimination in university activities.

The common aim of all is for a good, safe and just work and study atmosphere to prevail at the university. [...]

During the 2016–2018 period, the promotion of equality will become a more integrated part of Aalto’s quality management work. The Deans are responsible for equality work in their schools as part of their work on quality management [...]

https://www.aalto.fi/sites/g/files/flghsv161/files/2018-11/the_aalto_university_equality_plan_2016-2018.pdf

2.3 TARGET DIMENSIONS AND ACTIVITIES

In contrast to the two preceding chapters, the approach regarding diversity and gender equality in this chapter is divided into two different sub-chapters. This is due to the different possible answers for target dimensions and activities respectively.

For the questions on target dimensions, the number of possible answers was restricted to seven choices. The purpose was to get an idea of the relevance ranking of these target dimensions within our Members. Regarding the question on diversity and gender equality activities, the choice was not restricted to a certain number of items.

2.3.1 DIVERSITY

With regards to diversity target dimensions, respondents were able to choose up to seven items. The following graph shows their frequency distribution whereas items are listed according to the order in the survey questionnaire. The first nine items are general diversity objectives listed according to their relative importance. The last six items are targets for specific diversity dimensions.

Figure 2: Diversity target dimensions

Three items were mentioned by 20 or more participants: [strengthen gender equality](#), [assure non-discrimination and facilitate work-life balance, including family-friendliness](#). This result shows that gender equality is still the most important field of action - also when considered from a diversity perspective. Furthermore, within the participating universities, diversity management seems to have a strong focus on intersectionality and targets a broad range of diversity dimensions. Age and confessional diversity play an inferior role.

In table 2, we outline diversity activities in place at participating universities in 2016 and 2017. The survey allowed for multiple answers. The following table summarises the results according to the number of mentions (high, medium, and low). Items are presented in a shortened form. In the survey, most of them included examples (see Annex E: Equality Survey 2018 Questionnaire).

Table 2: Diversity activities

HIGH	Events on diversity	Development of diversity competence	Training programmes for students and lecturers	Draw up concepts or strategy papers
MEDIUM	Structural career programmes and mentoring for individuals from under-represented groups	Specific consulting services and appeal system	Monitoring of diversity	Provision of structural support
	Equal opportunities in recruiting processes	Consulting on diversity aspects in teaching and research	Development of guidelines for administrative action	Public relations
LOW	Specific measures and programmes for the promotion of individuals from under-represented groups	Setting of quota regulation or target figures	Funding for diversity-related research	
OTHERS	Development of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy and Strategy			

Twelve of the 15 proposed options are located in the 'high' and 'medium' category, whereas among the items in the 'high' category, two items were mentioned by more than 20 respondents: [organise events on diversity](#) and [develop diversity competence at your university](#). Furthermore, no item had zero clicks. When analysing the results of the survey, we can see that promotion of diversity is broadly anchored with the participating institutions. Obviously, awareness raising and competency development are frequently employed measures in diversity. This is not concurrent with the results of the evaluation of diversity target dimensions, where raising awareness and developing diversity competences were not among the most frequently mentioned items (cf. Figure 2). This highlights the often-simultaneous execution of activities and their impact at several levels and for different diversity dimensions. The following pages outline best practice examples for diversity initiatives.

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 5**University College Dublin - gender identity and expression**

The project included a broad range of activities:

- Development of gender identity and expression policy and guidelines in line with the university strategy and values;
- Undertaking a campaign to raise awareness around gender identity;
- Recognition of different gender identities through variety of measures;
- Equipping key members of University College Dublin (UCD) with skills and knowledge to implement the policy.

Examples of key actions are gender-neutral signage on single-stall facilities; documentation including gender options (Male/Female/Gender Non-binary/Self Declare_____/Prefer not to say); a culture and engagement survey incorporating nine equality grounds; and mandatory Equality Impact Assessment (EIA) for policy development.

<http://www.ucd.ie/equality/information/policies/genderidentityexpression>

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 6**University College Dublin - Equality Impact Assessment (EIA)**

An EIA is a systematic and evidence-based process which verifies that the university's policies and practices are non-discriminatory, fair and inclusive in meeting the legitimate needs of the diverse groups that make up the university community. It is a means of looking at university policies and practices systematically from a 'minority' group perspective and can highlight any potential inequalities which might not be obvious to someone looking at it from a 'majority' group perspective. Another key component of an EIA is to identify where a policy is promoting equality, diversity and inclusion in the university. The completion of an EIA is mandatory and is a requirement when seeking approval of a new or revised policy from the relevant approval body. If the EIA is not completed, the policy will not be approved.

<http://www.ucd.ie/equality/information/equalityimpactassessments/>

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 7***Politecnico di Torino* - Online survey 'Quality of organisational life'**

On the initiative of its Equal Opportunities Committee, *Politecnico di Torino* (PoliTo) launched the 'Survey on the quality of organisational life' with the scientific contribution of the Department of Psychology of the *Università degli Studi di Torino* in June 2017. It was addressed to all academic and technical-administrative staff. The aim was to collect opinions of those who work at the university regarding a list of indicators in order to define the quality of organisational life, highlighting elements that can positively or negatively affect the well-being of professors and staff.

https://www.swas.polito.it/services/cug/doc_cug.asp (in Italian)

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 8**University of Strathclyde - Family Friendly Research Leave (FFRL)**

Under the FFRL policy, eligible staff are entitled to a continuous period of up to three months paid research leave during which they have no teaching duties so that they are able to re-engage with their research duties. FFRL will normally commence on the individual's return from relevant family leave. Eligible staff can also access family-friendly mentoring support. The purpose is to support and encourage them in their professional development, provide advice on how to maximise the benefit of Keeping In Touch (KIT) and/or Shared Parental Leave In Touch (SPLIT) days, provide suggestions about how to maximise the benefit of the teaching backfill appointee, maintain and/or increase the confidence of the member of staff during relevant family leave and/or FFRL; provide practical advice, share experiences and provide suggestions on how to balance the demands of an academic staff role with family life.

https://www.strath.ac.uk/media/ps/humanresources/policies/Family_Friendly_Research_Leave_Policy.pdf

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 9**Poznan University of Technology - PUT around the world – Intercultural Café**

The Intercultural Café aims at integrating the academic community, cultural exchange and enlarge awareness about Poland among foreign students and awareness about the countries of origin of foreign students at Poznan University of Technology (PUT) among Polish students. During monthly meetings students give presentations about different topics like cuisine, music, wedding traditions, national games, hobbies, beautiful places and the influence of globalisation. There is time for discussion over a cup of coffee. There are two special editions for Christmas and Easter with presentations about celebrations of those holidays. Students make decorations and taste traditional food. Meetings are dedicated for both Polish and international students of PUT and universities in Poznan, as well as PUT employees.

<http://www.put.poznan.pl>

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 10**Ghent University - Coaching and diversity**

Community Service Learning is an educational approach that integrates service in the community with intentional learning activities. It offers the opportunity to integrate the original voluntary-based mentoring initiative into a curriculum-based learning experience. In 2013, the mentoring programme became an elective course (3 ECTS) for master students. The course 'Coaching and Diversity', includes (1) the practice of mentoring, (2) theoretical knowledge on diversity issues/ coaching techniques and (3) critical reflection. Master students practice their knowledge and skills by engaging as mentors for a first-year student in need of support and guidance. The course offers theoretical knowledge on diversity, conversation techniques, motivational speeches and didactics. Mentors learn to reflect critically on experiences, learning processes and civic engagement through a personal portfolio and planned peer-reviews.

www.ugent.be/coachingendiversiteit

2.3.2 GENDER EQUALITY

In this sub-chapter, we outline the findings for gender equality target dimensions and activities. The following chart illustrates gender equality target dimensions whereas items are listed according to response frequency. Up to seven answers were possible.

Figure 3: Gender equality target dimensions

The graph shows high approval ratings for more than half of the proposed response options. For *others*, the following dimensions were added: facilitation of work-life balance including family-friendliness, implement the gender perspective cross-cutting in all rules and statutes as well as UPM policies and integrate gender aspects in research & training; facilitate balancing of career/studies & family. The chart clearly illustrates that gender equality is based on a broad set of objectives and targeted from different angles, whereas changing academic and organisational culture is most important.

In the following table, we present gender equality activities in place at participating institutions in 2016 and 2017. Multiple mentions were possible. As for Table 2, the items are clustered and presented in shortened form.

Table 3: Gender equality activities

HIGH	Monitoring gender equality	Events on gender equality	Specific measures to attract female students to engineering studies	Development of gender competence
	Equal opportunities in recruiting processes	Structural career programmes and mentoring for women	Draw up concepts or strategy papers	Networking opportunities for female researchers
MEDIUM	Guidance on gender-neutral language in job descriptions	Public relations	Training programmes for students and lecturers	Consulting on the gender aspects of research proposals
	Specific consulting services and appeal system for female students or researchers	Specific measures and programmes to promote female talents	Setting of quotas to ensure a gender equal composition in committees	Development of guidelines for administrative action
	Setting of quota regulation or target figures	Structural support	Setting of quota regulations or target figures	
LOW	Funding for gender-related research			
OTHERS	“We work with ValoreD association (valored.it) to develop career opportunities for students” “We make surveys about gender equality”			

The table illustrates that of the 20 proposed items, 19 are in either in the ‘high’ or the ‘medium’ category. No item had zero mentions. *Monitoring gender equality* was the most frequently mentioned item for this question. This emphasis is reflected in Table 1, where we can see that of the 23 institutions with a GEP, 19 are evaluating its implementation.

Similar to diversity activities, the promotion of gender equality is broadly anchored within the participating institutions - not only in a quantitative but also in a qualitative sense: culture, system/organisation and personnel development including methods from affirmative action to regulations, from incentives to framework conditions.

2.3.3 COMPARISON

In this sub-chapter, we will briefly summarise and compare the results for target dimensions and activities for gender equality and diversity.

Starting with target dimensions, for diversity [assuring non-discrimination](#) is considered the most important target – for gender equality it is the second most important one. [Changing academic and organisational culture](#) is seen as the most important objective for gender equality – being amongst the second most important dimensions for diversity. Evidently these dimensions, simultaneously targeting a broad array of protected features, aim at sensitising all university members for cultural change to seep through all organisational structures.

Regarding activities, for both diversity and gender equality, the [drawing up of concepts and strategy papers](#) was among the most frequently mentioned initiatives in 2016 and 2017. This emphasis is mirrored in Table 1, showing that all participants either have GEP and/or DP or plan to develop these in the future. The monitoring of progress in gender equality and diversity plays an important role in the development of strategic papers and concepts, which is acknowledged and broadly implemented at universities of S&T (see Table 2 and Table 3).

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 11**ETH Zurich - Campaign 'Respect. Full stop.'**

Since 2004, ETH Zurich has run a series of RESPECT campaigns. The 2017/18 campaign was based on the slogan 'Respect. Full stop.' The aim was to encourage ETH staff to respect and never overstep personal boundaries. In a first phase the campaign used posters with attention-grabbing phrases and a short video clip was displayed in public spaces. The intention was to encourage ETH staff to reflect on personal boundaries and inappropriate behaviour as well as to stimulate discussion. A special webpage was published providing information about how to act respectfully as well as units to contact in cases of discrimination, bullying, violence or sexual harassment. In the following spring, the Code of Conduct - Respect was introduced to all ETH staff accompanied by a second video clip and a new series of posters displaying conflicting word pairs to highlight acceptable and unacceptable behaviour. In fall, all new ETH students received a small gift drawing attention to the website of the RESPECT Campaign. All material was produced in German and English. The posters were visible all across the institution and articles were launched in staff and student media. Furthermore, a competition to invent additional conflicting word pairs was organised.

www.respect.ethz.ch

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 12**University of Strathclyde - Equally Safe in Higher Education (ESHE)**

ESHE forms part of the Scottish Government's strategy for preventing and eradicating violence against women and girls. From 2016-2018, a toolkit was developed at the University of Strathclyde as pilot site. The toolkit provides a practical collection of free materials and resources were developed specifically for Scottish universities including tools on: developing a whole campus response, ESHE Research Tools, Gender Based Violence (GBV) Intervention, GBV Primary Prevention and GBV Curriculum and Knowledge Exchange. ESHE also develops awareness raising campaigns and GBV prevention education/training programmes for staff and students. As part of Strathclyde's implementation of the toolkit, we have produced a GBV Policy for staff, which has been accompanied by two levels of training on how to respond to GBV disclosures.

<https://www.strath.ac.uk/humanities/schoolofsocialworksocialpolicy/equallysafeinhighereducation/>

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 13**TU Wien - Men and women at TU Wien: figures, facts, analyses**

Since 2012, the Office for Gender Competence compiles the report 'Men and women at TU Wien: figures, facts, analyses' which comprises the following contents:

- Men/women quotas on graduation;
- Overview of the progress of the women's quota;
- Men/women quotas in scientific and non-scientific university staff;
- Men's/women's wages;
- Faculty reports and men/women quotas at the faculties;
- Students.

www.tuwien.ac.at/dle/genderkompetenz/zahlen_und_fakten/jahresberichte

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 14*Technische Universität Berlin - Joint Programmes*

Since 2014, TU Berlin offers a gender equality measure called 'Joint Programmes for Female Scientists & Professionals'. This programme promotes alternative career paths for women in academia and inter-sectoral collaboration. Visiting professorships aim at enabling women in research & development departments of business companies to build stronger networks with academia in order to increase the percentage of women at universities in the long-term. The programme promotes the permeability between industry and science and recruits female role models for the TU Berlin who pass their experience on to young talented researchers.

https://www.jointpro.tu-berlin.de/menue/joint_programmes/parameter/en/

BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLE 15*Aalto University – Shaking up Tech*

200 young women from various high schools in Finland took part in the first Shaking up Tech event at Aalto University on the International Day of the Girl on 11th October 2017. The goal of the event was to inspire and encourage talented young women to apply for studies in technology. With the event, Aalto University and partner companies wanted to shake the image that young people have of the field of technology, and show a glimpse of the many ways they can make a positive impact on the world by choosing a career in technology. The morning's talks from tech influencers outlined the various and exciting education and career opportunities in the field of technology. The event was continued with 18 parallel hands-on workshops where some of the participants got to combine mathematics and art, some had their first try at coding and others had a chance to produce a new kind of cellulose-based textile fibre from recycled materials. Finally, the event ended with a study fair where students got to know Aalto University's study opportunities and student life, and also met the event's partner companies. The event was inspired by the Teknologicamp of NTNU and it will be organised annually.

<https://shakinguptech.com/>

3 CURRENT AND FUTURE DRIVERS AND OBSTACLES OF EQUALITY

This chapter outlines the results of the more open part of the survey, including free-text fields for individual returns. First best practice examples are presented (1), then future steps to increase equality are outlined (2), further we will cluster and summarise internal and external activities that have best supported equality (3), followed by challenges and resistances faced when setting up equality measures (4).

(1) Looking at best practices, respondents were asked which three initiatives they would themselves define as best practices. All participants named best practices of their respective institution with an equal share of gender equality measures and measures targeting a broader field of diversity dimensions. In order to give an overview of the best practice examples received, these are clustered according to the gender equality and diversity activities in chapter 2.3 and only a few examples are outlined here. A full list of the examples can be found in the appendix (Annex F: List of best practice examples). A small number of best practice examples are outlined in more detail in the best practice boxes across the paper.

The most frequently mentioned best practices were examples for structural support and structural career programmes and mentoring. Examples for structural career programmes and mentoring came from Ghent University, KIT, KTH, LUH, RWTH, Strathclyde, TU Berlin, TU Braunschweig, TU Darmstadt, TU Delft, TU Graz, TU Wien and WUT. Exemplary structural support measures were provided by Aalto University EPFL, KTH, Polimi, PoliTo, PUT, RWTH, Strathclyde, TU Braunschweig, TU Delft and TU Graz. Best structural support measures are applied by Aalto, EPFL, KTH, PoliMi, PoliTo, PUT, RWTH, Strathclyde, TU Braunschweig, TU Darmstadt, TU Delft and TU Graz. In our evaluation, examples for structural career programmes and mentoring were mostly aimed towards women. Structural support measures often included work-family reconciliation measures such as childcare. Since these measures are accessible for a broad population of university members (and not only to women), we consider these initiatives to be diversity-relevant examples. Therefore, we consider that most of the self-assessed structural support best practices belong to diversity measures.

The summary and evaluation of best practices is mostly reflected in the results presented in chapter 2.3. For gender equality activities, structural career programmes and mentoring for women were ranked high (cf. Table 3) in the survey. The provision of structural support formed part of the medium-ranked items among diversity activities.

(2) In the following, we summarise the survey results regarding future aspirations to increase equality. First, we present them according to the target dimensions for gender equality and diversity (chapter 2.3). This gives an idea of the path gender equality and diversity management will possibly take in the future. Afterwards, the results are presented in clusters according to the activities named in chapter 2.3 - similar to the preceding paragraph.

In total 29 institutions listed future steps to increase equality. Structured according to the target dimensions evaluated in chapter 2.3, five future target areas are most prominent: [change organisational structures and processes](#), [change academic and organisational culture](#), [reduce under-representation](#), [raise awareness and develop competencies](#) as well as [strengthen gender equality](#) (For a full list of future steps, see Annex G: Future steps to increase equality).

Those were also frequently mentioned items for diversity and gender equality target dimensions. Interestingly, [assure non-discrimination](#) was ranked as high priority both for diversity and gender equality in 2.3. Yet in this evaluation it did not come up as one of the most prominently mentioned categories. The same applies to [protect from sexual abuse](#), which was of low future relevance but among the three most frequently mentioned target dimensions for gender equality. Possible explanations are the overlap and interweaving of the target areas. The fact that assurance of non-discrimination and protection from sexual abuse were not ranked as top future priorities does not necessarily mean that nothing is going to be done. They are possibly already tackled as aspects of other objectives. Nevertheless, this does not imply that these topics do not require separate room for discussion. Moreover, the results reveal that three areas do not seem to be of great importance in the future of equality work. These are [foster inclusion of confessional diversity](#), [strengthen age diversity](#) and [protect from sexual abuse](#). Regarding [confessional diversity](#) and [age diversity](#), an identical picture was found in chapter 2.3 with zero mentions respectively. Here we are raising caution towards the categorisation of the results. In order to summarise the free-text responses of this part, we interpret and quantify the rather qualitative and openly formulated answers. Therefore, we apply great care, but nevertheless we cannot guarantee the correct assignment of all categories to the respective activities all of the time.

When we analyse future steps to increase equality from another point of view according to the activities named in chapter 2.3, we see that planned activities were almost equally distributed regarding gender equality and diversity - with a slightly higher number of activities taken to focus on gender equality. Drawing up and revising concepts and strategy papers were by far the most frequently envisaged activities. The papers and concepts targeted gender equality and diversity with almost equal frequency. Table 1 in chapter 2.2 underpins this result. All participating universities expressed that they either already have a GEP and DP or – for those who did not – are planning to develop them in the future. [Equal opportunities in recruiting processes](#), [development of equality competencies](#) and the [provision of structural support](#) came up as further future focus areas with far less activities assigned to each category. Overall, these results are in line with the evaluation of diversity and gender equality activities in chapter 2.3. *Drawing up concepts and strategy papers* has been among the most frequently named activities for 2016/2017 – for diversity as well as gender equality. The [development of competencies](#), [equal opportunities in recruitment processes](#) and [provision of structural support](#) were among the most to medium frequently named activities in 2016/2017.

(3) Regarding successful external and internal activities, the survey revealed a rather balanced field of internal and external activities supporting equality. The most frequently named successful internal activities were structural measures. Examples included the embedding and commitment to gender equality and diversity at the level of university leaders, e.g. at TU Berlin and RWTH, installation of specific departments or entities responsible for gender equality and/or diversity e.g. gender vanguards at KU Leuven as well as the very close collaboration between the centralised and decentralised level of the university at TU Darmstadt (for a full list, see [Annex H: Internal and external push- and pull-factors](#)). These qualitative results underpin the quantitative findings of chapter 2.1. They emphasise the importance of anchoring gender equality and diversity in the organisational structure of the university, best at the level of the top university leadership.

Regarding successful external activities promoting equality the most frequently named measures were public relations activities and events. Amongst these, measures targeted towards girls with the aim to inspire and encourage them to pursue a career in STEM were most prominent. Furthermore, legal regulations were considered successful external measures in promoting equality. This was mostly the case in central and northern European countries. For these universities federal and regional federal legislation was regarded an important driving factor for equality, e.g. University Acts of the German Federal States, norms by the Swedish state and regional federal governments. For German universities the Excellence Initiative provides funding in order to promote research of the highest international standards, enhance research profiles and to facilitate research cooperation (*Deutsche Forschungsgesellschaft*, 2019), as well as the research-oriented Standards on Gender Equality by the DFG as central research-funding organisation were considered successful external measures.

(4) Regarding challenges and internal barriers more than half (57%) indicated that they were not facing internal barriers. 43% or 13 participants confirmed that they faced internal resistance when setting up equality initiatives. The thirteen respondents which confirmed that they had experienced internal resistance were subsequently asked to categorise the barriers into six categories. The categories and results are shown in Figure 4. Multiple choices were possible.

Figure 4: Types of internal barriers or resistance impeding the promotion of equality

The most frequently mentioned barrier was [lack of awareness of gender inequality or diversity issues](#). Taking a look at named diversity and gender equality activities in chapter 2.3, we can see that universities of S&T are not only aware of barriers, but also actively work to reduce their influence, e.g. by organising events and competency development. Looking at individual responses all 13 respondents named two or more barriers, with three barriers on average. This illustrates that when institutions face barriers these are encountered in different areas and at different levels. Five respondents named other barriers. These were: cultural barriers in engineering studies regarding women, responsibilities in decentralised structures are often not clear, lack of ownership by management, unconscious bias in recruiting and career planning, as well as prevailing masculine values at the university.

Our analysis also reveals that those universities with a long tradition in equality work usually face more barriers. We hypothesise that this is because of a more sensitised and thus critical mind-set of their equality players, paired with the high amount of activities performed in different areas of the university, thus potentially leading to more resistances.

Finally, the survey asked for [any other comments](#) that participants would like to share. The comments can be summarised into two broad fields. Firstly, respondents raised the concern that they lacked resources in order to implement equality measures. Secondly, lack of awareness and competencies among all university members and the need for training and sensitisation measures are considered further points worth sharing.

4 STATE OF PLAY AT MEMBERS

The last part of the Equality Survey 2018 asked for quantitative data in order to record the state of play of gender equality at our Members in 2017. Data is requested at the level of the university as a whole. Our Members are universities of S&T and some of them may also host faculties and institutions outside of STEM. This has to be taken into account when analysing and interpreting the results.

The structure of this part of the survey is based on the preceding survey of 2014 and asks for figures on academic management, administrative management, appointment committees, scientific staff, students and graduates, ERC grantees, Marie Skłodowska-Curie fellows and Horizon 2020 project coordinators. For diversity it was assumed that most universities do not collect structured data. Therefore, an open question has been added in the 2018 survey.

Where possible, survey data is compared to the STEM figures for 2016 of the She Figures 2018 report issued by the European Commission (2019).

4.1 ACADEMIC AND ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT

With respect to top academic management, five of 31 responding universities have a female president, rector or equivalent whereas 26 employ a male counterpart. The proportion of women at this level is 16.1%. At the level of vice-rectors (academic management level 2) a total number of 151 vice-rectors has been reported whereof 52 women. The share of women therefore is at 34.4%. At the subsequent academic management level (e.g. deans) a total of 521 incumbents has been calculated. Thereof, 124 are women amounting to a proportion of women of 23.8%.

For administrative management, figures for administrative directors or equivalent and administrative management level 2, e.g. head of department, were asked. At the top administrative management level, the gender distribution is four women among 27 administrative directors (27 universities replied to this question) resulting in a share of women of 14.8%. At the second level of administrative management, e.g. heads of department, the Equality Survey 2018 evaluation shows a total of 590 managers whereof 283 women - making up 48%.

Figure 5 shows the average share of women at second and third academic and second administrative level and the amount of universities that have a share below 30%, between 30 and 50% and over 50%. A share of 30% is seen as a 'critical mass' for the representation of women in a board (Wallon, Bendiscioli and Garfinkel, 2015, p.11). The threshold of 50% means equal participation or parity. Thus, the chart and the accompanying average share of women illustrate that gender balance is not yet reached. Nevertheless, there are a few remarkable findings: at the second level of academic management the share of women is considerable with almost half of the respondents reporting a female participation between 30% and 50% (11) and over 50% (4). Moreover, at administrative management level 2 the participation of women is even higher with 13 respondents claiming a proportion of women between 30 and 50% and 12 respondents over 50%.

Figure 5: Comparison of proportion of women at different academic and administrative management levels

In summary, we claim that the proportion of women is higher in leadership committees (e.g. vice-rectorates) as opposed to single leadership positions (e.g. rector, dean). It is possible that gender equal participation is more enforced in committees as opposed to leadership positions. In some countries, such as Germany and Austria, equal representation in committee work is required by law through quotas. Furthermore, leadership positions, such as vice-rector or head of administrative department, seem to be an attractive career path for women. Yet under-representation of women in academic and administrative leadership remains considerable, especially in decision-making positions.

4.2 APPOINTMENT COMMITTEES FOR PROFESSORSHIPS

In order to get an idea of female committee involvement, the survey asked for the number of female appointment committee members for professorships. 21 respondents reported a total number of 643 processes in which 25.9% of committee members were women (2,838 appointment committee members whereof 734 women). The next pie chart shows the distribution of the proportion of women among participating Members.

Figure 6: Proportion of women in appointment committees in professorships

Evidently, only one university has parity or a female majority in appointment committees and more than half of the respondents have a share of women of less than 30%. Consequently, equal participation of women in decision-making processes is not reached. For the majority of universities of S&T in our sample, more has to be done to increase the concentration of women in such committees.

4.3 STUDENTS AND GRADUATES

Table 4 shows the number of students (including Bachelor, Master and PhD students) and graduates at several levels. Overall, the share of female students is slightly declining by a little more than a third at PhD level.

Moreover, the table compares the results to the STEM figures of She Figures 2018 and the last column shows the figures for students and graduates across Bachelor, Master and doctoral level in the field of STEM as reported by the European Commission (2019, p.117). Here, this comparison is viable since categories of students correspond to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) level 6 at Bachelor's level or equivalent, ISCED level 7 being Master's or equivalent and ISCED 8 as PhD/doctoral level (European Commission, 2019, p.187).

Table 4: Proportion of women for all students and graduates at Bachelor, Master and PhD level

CATEGORY	NUMBER OF UNIVERSITIES CONTRIBUTING VALID DATA	TOTAL	WOMEN		EU-28, STEM, 2016 ¹
		NUMBER	NUMBER	%	% OF WOMEN
Students	29	725207	256374	35.4%	32%/37% ²
Graduates					
Bachelor	29	78408	27582	35.2%	36%
Master	29	79761	28294	35.5%	
PhD/doctoral	30	11555	3775	32.7%	39%

Overall, the results of the survey correspond to the findings of She Figures 2018. However, there are obvious differences in the proportion of women for PhD graduates. We discuss challenges and limitations to this comparison in paragraph 4.5.

4.4 SCIENTIFIC STAFF

In this paper and survey, we have adopted the structure of scientific staff from the She Figures issued by the European Commission. Here, grade D is considered the lowest level, including postgraduate students not yet holding a PhD or researchers in a position not requiring a PhD, Grade C includes positions requiring a PhD such as assistant professors, postdocs or equivalent, Grade B summarises associate professors or equivalent and Grade A implies the level of full professors or equivalent as the highest position “at which research is normally conducted” (European Commission, 2019, p.190). The following table shows the proportion of women according to scientific grade and compares the share of women with the numbers reported by the European Commission (2019).

Table 5: Proportion of women for scientific staff grade A to D

GRADE	NUMBER OF UNIVERSITIES CONTRIBUTING VALID DATA	TOTAL	WOMEN		EU-28, STEM, 2016 ³
		NUMBER	NUMBER	SHARE	SHARE OF WOMEN
D	29	42457	14720	34.7%	- ⁴
C	28	9719	2948	30.3%	35%
B	29	8807	2463	28.0%	28%
A	30	7614	1268	16.7%	15%

Table 5 illustrates that women are underrepresented in all grades at our Members. While they make up a third in grade D, only 16.7% of female researchers reach grade A. Comparing the data to the EU-28 as reported in the She Figures 2018, we can see a close congruence apart from grade C (European Commission, 2016, p. 133). However, there is a limitation to this comparison since the content of the grade categories varies between European countries, i.e. in some countries, Assistant Professors belong to grade C in others to grade D.

¹ European Commission, 2019, p.117.

² Proportion of women at Bachelor's and Master's level at 32%; proportion of women at PhD level at 37%, both for STEM.

³ European Commission, 2019, p.117.

⁴ No information available for STEM.

4.5 PROPORTION OF WOMEN ALONG ACADEMIC CAREER PATH

This sub-chapter discusses the development of the proportion of women from student to professor level grade A. The following chart compares the results from this survey to the She Figures 2018. Evidently, the higher one climbs the scientific career ladder, the lower the participation of female researchers.

Figure 7: Proportion of women and men in academic careers at Members and EU-28 in STEM

Overall, the survey results correspond to the figures reported in the She Figures 2018. Yet we can also see differences especially for students, PhD graduates and scientific staff at grade C. Moreover, She Figures 2018 do not report number for grade D in STEM. Limitations to the comparison of EU-28 figures with the survey results possibly stem from numerous grounds: firstly, the population of participating Members is not necessarily representative for all European universities of S&T; secondly some Members are not entire universities but rather faculties or institutes of science and technology. In this survey, we requested numbers of the university as a whole. Consequently, figures from university areas outside of STEM could impact on our findings. Thirdly, when checking the survey dataset, we found partially inconsistent data for individual institutions. Finally, we cannot be sure that numbers accumulated across different European countries will yield fully comparable and interpretable results, e.g. scientific staff grades A to D vary from country to country. In spite of everything, overall the figures collected in this survey deliver meaningful results that are mostly in line with the findings at EU-28 level.

4.6 WOMEN IN HORIZON 2020

Here we outline the representation of women in Horizon 2020. The survey requested figures on grantees sponsored by the European Research Council (ERC) funding instrument – one of the most important research scholarships in Europe –, incoming and outgoing fellows of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie fellowship as well as Horizon 2020 Project Coordinators.

The following table shows the number of universities contributing data, the total number of grantees, fellows and project coordinators, the total number of women as well as the proportion of women for our Members and EU-28 respectively.

Table 6: Proportion of women across Horizon 2020 grants

HORIZON 2020	UNIVERSITIES CONTRIBUTING VALID DATA	TOTAL	WOMEN		EU-28 ⁵
	NUMBER	NUMBER	NUMBER	%	%
ERC Starting grantees	26	190	50	26.3%	31%
ERC Consolidator grantees	27	113	27	23.9%	29%
ERC Advanced grantees	9	75	6	8.0%	16%
MSCA outgoing fellows	19	72	17	23.6%	41.9%
MSCA incoming fellows	22	476	115	24.2%	
Horizon 2020 Project Coordinators	22	560	99	17.7%	35.1% ⁶

As the table shows the number of contributing universities varies significantly between the different programmes resulting in different totals from which the proportion of women has been calculated. Therefore, the proportion of women requires critical consideration. Nevertheless, the numbers illustrate yet again the underrepresentation of women in the science system and particularly in higher research positions. As a result, women are less likely than men to apply for research funding since many funding schemes are restricted to academic staff at higher levels of the research system (Ranga, Gupta and Etzkowitz, 2012). The very low and declining numbers of female researchers holding ERC grants is not surprising when we consider the decreasing concentration of female scientific staff from grade C to A at universities of S&T (chapter 4.4). Before concluding this chapter, we would like to relativise these findings. Horizon 2020 grants are not necessarily relevant measures across all universities and for all areas. Some universities in our sample are very active and successful whereas the majority of universities are without funding. Compared to the EU-28, we can see that the numbers resulting from the survey are below EU-28 figures provided by the European Commission during a personal communication (April 24, 2019). Note that EU-28 figures are not limited to the area of STEM and include other subject fields.

4.7 DIVERSITY DATA

An open question asked for data on the diversity amongst university members in order to approach the currently little standardised field of diversity data collection. Of the 27 universities that replied to this question, 25 collect such data. The most frequently documented diversity dimensions are age (14), disability (14) and nationality (6). Other recorded dimensions include ethnicity, religion and belief, sexual orientation and gender reassignment family and civil status as well as socioeconomic status. Interestingly, exclusively respondents from the UK and Ireland collect an entire range of data for different diversity dimensions. Links to the best practice examples for diversity data collection can be found in Annex K: Diversity data best practice examples.

⁵ European Commission (personal communication, April 24, 2019)

⁶ European Commission, 2018, p.173.

5 COMPARISON OF EQUALITY SURVEY 2014 AND 2018

Here we compare the results of the Gender Equality Survey conducted in 2014 with the Equality Survey of 2018 where possible. Note that comparison is done for gender equality only since the diversity aspect was newly included in the 2018 survey.

5.1 RESPONSIBILITIES, STRATEGIES AND MEASURES IN GENDER EQUALITY

This first comparative chapter looks at structural embedding of gender equality, Gender Equality Plans and activities.

Regarding the structural anchoring of gender equality, the 2014 and 2018 survey proposed a different number of items with nine response options in 2018 and six in 2014. The 2018 survey had the following items added: rector or equivalent, deans/faculties, gender equality commission and external advisory group. In contrast to 2018, the 2014 questionnaire included an option to name *other forms of organisation*. Consequently, there are limitations towards this comparison. In the 2014 survey, 16 universities expressed that they had a unit dealing with gender equality among broader responsibilities and 15 employed a special unit for gender equality. The picture looks different in the 2018 results: the most frequently named embedding of gender equality was at the rectorate and at deanships/faculties. A special organisational unit for gender equality occupied the third rank and a unit with broader responsibilities the fifth rank after a commission that deals with gender equality. In conclusion, a special organisational unit for gender equality still seems to be an important organisational structure amongst participating Members, ranking third in 2018 after rectorate and deanship responsibility.

In the following table, we will take a look at the strategic underpinning of gender equality by comparing the prevalence of GEPs in 2014 and 2018. Therefore, Table 7 lists the participating Members in the 2014 and 2018 survey. 45 institutions completed the survey in 2014 and 31 in 2018 – thereof 28 participated in both surveys. Furthermore, it summarises and opposes the prevalence of Gender Equality Plans and Diversity Plans 2014 and 2018 respectively. The universities are clustered into eight groups. The groups are listed in alphabetical order according to country of origin.

Table 7: GEP and DP at our Members in 2014 and 2018

INSTITUTION	COUNTRY	2014		2018		
		PARTICIPATION	GEP	PARTICIPATION	GEP	DP
PARTICIPATION IN 2014 AND 2018; GEP IN 2014, GEP AND/OR DP IN 2018						
TU Wien	AT	•	•	•	•	•
UGent	BE	•	•	•	•	•
KU Leuven	BE	•	•	•	•	•
EPFL	CH	•	•	•	•	•
ETH Zurich	CH	•	•	•	•	
KIT	DE	•	•	•	•	
LUH	DE	•	•	•	•	•
RWTH	DE	•	•	•	•	•
TU Berlin	DE	•	•	•	•	
TU Braunschweig	DE	•	•	•	•	
TU Darmstadt	DE	•	•	•	•	
UPC	ES	•	•	•	•	•
Aalto	FI	•	•	•	•	•
TU Delft	NL	•	•	•		•
NTNU	NO	•	•	•	•	•
Chalmers	SE	•	•	•	•	•
KTH	SE	•	•	•	•	•
PARTICIPATION IN 2014 AND 2018; NO GEP IN 2014, GEP AND/OR DP IN 2018						
UPM	ES	•		•	•	
UPV	ES	•		•	•	
INSA Lyon	FR	•		•	•	•
UCD	IRL	•		•	•	•
PoliMi	IT	•		•	•	•
PARTICIPATION IN 2014 AND 2018; GEP IN 2014, NEITHER GEP NOR DP IN 2018						
BME	HU	•	•	•		
PoliTo	IT	•	•	•		
PARTICIPATION IN 2018 WITH GEP AND DP IN 2018						
TU Graz	AT			•	•	•
Strathclyde	UK			•	•	•
PARTICIPATION IN 2014 AND 2018 (OR 2018 ONLY); NO GEP IN 2014, NEITHER GEP NOR DP IN 2018						
TalTech	EE	•		•		
KTU	LT	•		•		
PUT	PL	•		•		
WUT	PL	•		•		
RTU	LV			•		

Of the 28 institutions participating in both surveys, 17 had GEP and DP in place in 2014 and 2018. Moreover, their implementation is evaluated in almost all cases (highlighted in grey). Five of the 28 that did not have a GEP in 2014 indicated to have GEP and DP in 2018. Among them, four evaluate their implementation. Of the universities that only participated in 2014, seven had GEP and 13 did not have GEP in place. More details can be found in the report presenting the results of the Gender Equality Survey 2014 (Horvat, 2015).

The comparison reveals questionable results, e.g. two universities indicated GEP in 2014, but neither GEP nor DP in 2018. A possible explanation is that the 2014 and 2018 surveys employ

different ways of inquiry and methods of evaluation for the questions on GEP and DP potentially leading to inconsistency in the results.

Overall, we can see that GEP are wider spread than DP and we can assume that this is the case due to EU or national regulations. At EU level, and in many European countries, gender equality is more regulated by law than diversity. Furthermore, diversity is a relatively new field of action compared to gender equality.

In the 2018 survey, the questions on target dimensions like the diversity aspect were newly included. Therefore, in the following, we are comparing gender equality activities in 2014 and 2018. In the 2014 survey, the most prominent gender equality activities were (1) work-life balance; (2) measures to attract female students to engineering studies and (3) gender competencies together with networking opportunities for female researchers. In the 2018 survey, more response options were given. Nevertheless, (2) and (3) still were in the [high](#) category in 2018 and [structural support measures](#) improving the work and family reconciliation in the [medium](#) category. The comparison illustrates the long-term character of gender equality management at universities of S&T once again. Moreover, the issue is and has been tackled from different angles and a holistic point of view.

5.2 BEST PRACTICES, FUTURE STEPS AND BARRIERS

Due to the added diversity aspect in the 2018 survey, open questions on self-assessed best practices and future steps asked for initiatives and future steps to increase equality including gender equality and diversity. In contrast, the 2014 survey required [‘Gender Equality’ initiatives as examples of best practices](#) as well as [next steps about ‘Gender Equality’](#). Nevertheless, yields congruent results and thus illustrates the persistent and multi-layered effort to establish (gender) equality.

Regarding self-assessed best practice examples, structural career programmes and mentoring for women as well as structural career support such as home office, maternity leave and family-friendly services were the most frequently named groups of initiatives.

The comparison of future steps to increase (gender) equality reveals similar results for 2014 and 2018. In both survey rounds, drawing up and revising concepts and strategy papers was the most frequently named plan for the future. A focus on recruiting processes and competency development played their part in both surveys.

Regarding barriers and resistances, the 2014 survey asked for barriers in connection with gender issues, whereas the 2018 survey interrogated barriers related to equality issues (including gender equality and diversity). Another difference in the examination was that only three of the proposed options in 2014 were provided in 2018: (i) [Regulations or policies at national or regional level do not allow or support gender equality \[...\] activities](#), (ii) [lack \[of\] resources to implement measures on gender equality \[...\]](#) and (iii) [internal resistance against gender equality \[...\] measures](#). Finally, the 2014 survey asked for a rating of these barriers (important, somewhat important, not important) whereas in 2018 it was a simple multiple-choice question. We refrained from this weighting in the 2018 survey since we found it difficult to assign to the different items and did not perceive advantages for the evaluation of barriers.

Therefore, the following comparison is conditionally interpretable. In 2014, 18 of 42 (42.8%) respondents affirmed that they face barriers. This is equivalent to the proportion reported in

2018, where 13 of 30 (43.3%) respondents indicated that they faced resistances. In terms of the types of barriers that were faced, in 2014 internal resistance and lack of resources were the most important issues whereas in 2018 lack of awareness came before internal resistance. Note that the 2014 survey did not provide lack of awareness as response option. Lack of resources played an inferior role (5 mentions) in 2018, which might be due to other items added: [lack of awareness of gender inequality and diversity issues](#) and [responsibilities within the university are not clear](#). Remarkably, the free-text field [any other comments](#) in Part III of the 2018 survey was used to express concerns about lacking resources for the implementation of measures and about the lack of awareness and competencies among all university members. Hence, we can say that nothing has significantly changed regarding barriers and resistances from 2014 to 2018, whereas a lack of awareness and resources as well as internal resistance have been and currently are the most frequently faced barriers.

In summary, the analysis and comparison of best practices, future aspirations and barriers show the long-term nature of the process and the persistence of barriers impeding equality. Members tackle gender (in-) equality with stamina, from different angles and with a strategic point of view.

5.3 PROPORTION OF WOMEN IN SCIENCE

In this sub-chapter, we compare statistical data collected in the 2014 survey with statistical data from 2018. The structure of this chapter is analogous to chapter 4. Of the 31 universities participating in 2018, 28 also contributed to the 2014 survey. The opportunities and challenges of the comparison are discussed in a separate paragraph at the end.

5.3.1 ACADEMIC AND ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT

Table 8 compares figures for academic and administrative management in the 2014 survey (academic year 2012/13) and the 2018 survey (calendar year 2017). We can see that no comparison was made for academic management level 3 (e.g. deans) and administrative management level 2 (e.g. heads of administrative departments). The reason is that the 2014 survey exclusively required percentage numbers and the 2018 survey asked for absolute numbers from which the share of women has been calculated.

Table 8: Comparison of proportion of women for academic and administrative management

LEVEL	2014			2018		
	TOTAL	WOMEN		TOTAL	WOMEN	
	NUMBER	NUMBER	SHARE	NUMBER	NUMBER	SHARE
Rector	45	5	11.9%	31	5	16.1 %
Vice-rector	181	41	22.7%	151	52	34.4%
Dean	Comparison not possible					
Administrative director	40	13	32.5%	27	4	14.8%
HO admin. dep.	Comparison not possible					

Apparently, there has been an increase of around 4% in the proportion of women at the level of rectors or equivalent. Note that the absolute number of female rectors has remained the same. At the level of vice-rectors, we can see an increase in the representation of women in relative (approx. 12%) and absolute terms. For this group, absolute figures allow for a better comparison. For top administrative management, we can see an obvious decrease of female administrative heads from 2012/13 to the calendar year 2017 of 15%. In 2014, 40 universities contributed data; 27 replied in 2018. After verifying the accuracy of the numbers, we conclude that the data does not represent the long-term development of women in this position. Potential methodological explanations are outlined in 5.3.6 where we discuss the opportunities and challenges of this comparison.

Note that no comparative analysis is performed for the representation of women in appointment committees for professorships. This is due to the different ways the questions were asked in 2014 and 2018. In the 2014 survey, [requirements for gender diversity in appointment committees](#) were requested whereas in 2018 we required the number of processes, appointment committee members as well as female appointment committee members in order to get a clear view on the status-quo of the share of women in appointment committees and to evaluate equal representation in such committees.

5.3.2 STUDENTS AND GRADUATES

The numbers for students and graduates are compared in this part of the white paper. The table shows absolute and relative numbers for both surveys.

Table 9: Comparison of the proportion of women for students, Bachelor, Master and PhD graduates

LEVEL	2014			2018		
	TOTAL	WOMEN		TOTAL	WOMEN	
	NUMBER	NUMBER	%	NUMBER	NUMBER	%
Students ⁷	168028	58913	35.1%	725207	256374	35.6%
GRADUATES						
Bachelor	73105	24663	33.7%	78408	27582	35.2%
Master	44066	15716	35.7%	79761	28294	35.5%
PhD/Doctoral	12414	4072	32.8%	11555	3775	32.7%

Concerning students, the comparison between 2014 and 2018 reveals a slight increase in the proportion of women. However, the absolute numbers from which the percentages were calculated vary significantly: in 2014 absolute numbers were collected for first-year students (new entrants) whereas in the 2018 survey, student data included all Bachelor, Master and PhD students. Nevertheless, the commuted percentage seems reasonable. The comparison of graduate numbers shows minor changes in percentages at all levels. The increase in the in the proportion of female bachelor graduates by 1.5% is most notable. Due to the comparable absolute numbers, we can assume that the change is not merely due to deterioration in the data but that more women are actually graduating in STEM at Member institutions. Yet this development is not reflected in the numbers at Master graduate level.

⁷ For 2014 only first year students (new entrants) are considered.

Considering that absolute numbers differ greatly for this group, we can question the direction and extent of change at this level. At PhD level, the data reveals an apparent non-existing change in the proportion of women - whereby absolute data is comparable.

5.3.3 SCIENTIFIC STAFF

In the 2014 survey, data for scientific staff was equally structured according to career level: full professors (or equivalent), associate professors (or equivalent), assistant professors (or equivalent) and other scientific staff.

Table 10: Comparison of the proportion of women for scientific staff

GRADE	2014			2018		
	TOTAL	WOMEN		TOTAL	WOMEN	
	NUMBER	NUMBER	%	NUMBER	NUMBER	%
D	42594	12718	29.9%	42457	14720	34.7%
C	9784	3156	32.3%	9719	2948	30.3%
B	11025	2941	26.7%	8807	2463	28.0%
A	9308	1408	15.2%	7614	1268	16.7%

The table shows that, from 2014 to 2018, there has been a slight increase in the proportion of women, except for grade C where the percentage fell by 2%. This tendency can be confirmed when taking into account absolute numbers, which are comparable across all grades.

5.3.4 PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN ALONG ACADEMIC CAREER PATH

In this sub-chapter, we contrast data regarding the proportion of women from students up to grade A scientific staff from 2014 and 2018. Due to differing data sets, as well as a different cohort of participating institutions, a comparative perspective is adopted with caution and where data allows. The 2014 survey requested figures for the academic year 2012/2013, whereas for the 2018 Equality Survey the reporting period was the calendar year 2017.

Figure 8: Proportion of women along the academic career ladder for 2014 and 2018

As elaborated in the previous sub-chapters, Figure 8 allows for mixed conclusions regarding the development of the proportion of women along the academic career path at our Members in the four-year period.

Minor to no changes are visible at the level of students and graduates, with a slight increase in female students and female bachelor graduates. This picture illustrates that the challenge of increasing the proportion of women in higher ranks of academia already starts at the entrance into STEM study. We consider the entry point for women into academia a key area of future focus in order to increase the proportion of women higher up in the hierarchy. Only when qualified and motivated women enter academic studies in STEM, will there be a steady supply of women ready to take on leadership positions within Member institutions and beyond.

Nevertheless, activities targeted towards career development of female researchers already in the science system seem to be fruitful. We can see an upward trend at grade D, B and A. Zooming into the development of the proportion of female scientific staff, the following chart shows remarkable changes at grade D and A: a change of five percentage points (i.e. an increase by 16.7%) at grade D and a two-percentage-point change at grade A (i.e. an increase of 13%). We consider these changes to be remarkable due to the slow pace of change in gender equality in general, as well as the numerous and robust challenges faced within this process, especially at full professor level (barriers and resistances are outlined in chapter 3 and 5.1).

Figure 9: Comparison of the proportion of women from grade D to A

5.3.5 WOMEN IN FP7 AND HORIZON 2020

Below we compare the participation of women in FP7 and Horizon 2020 grants collected by the 2014 and 2018 survey. For better comparability, the table below shows absolute numbers.

Table 11: Comparison of the proportion of women for FP7 and Horizon 2020

	FP7			HORIZON 2020		
	TOTAL	WOMEN		TOTAL	WOMEN	
	NUMBER	NUMBER	%	NUMBER	NUMBER	%
ERC Starting grantees	184	32	17.5%	190	50	26.3%
ERC Consolidator grantees	30	3	10.0%	113	27	23.9%
ERC Advanced grantees	136	14	10.4%	75	6	8.0%
MSCA outgoing fellows	121	27	22.2%	72	17	23.6%
MSCA incoming fellows	343	72	21.1%	476	115	24.2%
FP7/Horizon 2020 Project Coordinators	463	94	20.4%	560	99	17.7%

The comparison of absolute figures shows that we have to draw careful conclusions regarding the development of the proportion of women - especially for ERC Consolidator grantees, ERC Advanced grantees and Marie Skłodowska-Curie outgoing fellows. Regarding ERC Starting grantees, we can see an increase of almost 9% from 2014 to 2018. This figure is quite surprising since the proportion of women at grade C - which would be eligible for such a grant - dropped in 2018 compared to the 2014 results. For Marie Skłodowska-Curie incoming fellows, numbers rose by approximately 3% and for FP7/Horizon 2020 project coordinators the share of women dropped by almost 3%.

5.3.6 OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

There are several methodological limitations of this comparative perspective on the proportion of women at our Members potentially explaining some of the contradictory results. First, 28 of the 31 universities participating in 2018 contributed to the 2014 survey. These 28 make up around two-thirds of participants in 2014. Consequently, the results of 2014 also contain data from institutions not reflected in the 2018 dataset. Secondly, the surveys considered different periods of time: the academic year 2012/13 in the 2014 survey and the 2018 survey, questions either required data at reporting date 31st December 2017 or for the calendar year 2017. This divergent approach was taken because some figures can only be reported at reporting dates e.g. the proportion of female researchers. Thirdly, the survey questions were partially different in 2014 and 2018, e.g. percentages requested versus absolute figures for deans and heads of administrative departments. Furthermore, we are sometimes missing data or data 2014 and 2018 is not compatible e.g. administrative directors. Finally, in the slow process of cultural and societal change, an evaluation period of four years (2014 to 2018) is short and potentially too short to expect dramatic changes in the representation of women in areas where women are traditionally under-represented. Despite these limitations, the comparison of statistical data affords several opportunities. It lays the foundation for further discussion among university leaders and HR professionals. It allows for further progress by pointing out specific areas needing intensified leadership attention and more targeted measures by HR professionals. Finally, it may also feed into the discussion at the level of European policymakers and gender

equality actors. Therefore, specific recommendations are formulated in the following concluding chapter.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

We conclude that gender equality and diversity are established fields of action at our Member institutions. Structural embedding shows that university leadership has taken on the responsibility to accomplish equality in many universities of S&T. Moreover, gender equality and diversity are increasingly tackled from a strategic perspective. In 2018, all participating universities either have GEP and DP in place, plan to develop these or have equality enshrined in their university strategy. The evolving strategic focus on equality has been further highlighted in the future plans to draw up and/or revise strategy papers and concepts.

Not only does this paper show the significance of leadership commitment and a strategic approach for equality, it further points towards the importance of EU and national legislation. Firstly, there are EU-wide differences to the degree of strategic anchoring: most universities with existing strategy papers stem from old EU member states. Secondly, there are regional differences in the prevalence of GEP and DP illustrating the different *foci* of national legislation on gender equality and diversity. Furthermore, we can see that the current national legislation of several European countries (e.g. Austria, Germany, Sweden) is focused on gender equality. This is not only reflected in the prevalence of GEP over DP in our sample but also the significance of gender equality as a target dimension – even from a diversity perspective. Moreover, there is a long-standing tradition of gender equality measures among our Members and a number of self-assessed best practice examples mostly targeted towards career development for women and towards reconciling family and work responsibilities. Nevertheless, the newly included part on diversity illustrates that diversity is also on the agenda of universities of S&T. This field of action is not neglected and the various issues are tackled by means of numerous measures for multiple diversity dimensions and targeting a broad population of stakeholders at different levels inside and outside of academia.

Despite all efforts, barriers and resistances persist, and progress in equal participation of women in S&T remains slow. This is one of the main results from the evaluation of statistical data: almost no change was visible for the level of students and graduates pointing towards a need for more actions aimed at these target groups. Slight changes were evident at the level of scientific staff from grade D to A, suggesting that measures targeted towards female researchers bear fruit. The analysis of women in European research funding indicates a considerable underrepresentation of women. The numbers mirror the low concentration of women at high-graded research positions in comparison to men, making them less likely to be eligible for research funding schemes by the main research funding institutions. Finally, looking at academic and administrative top management, we see that under-representation of women in academic and administrative leadership is substantial, especially for single decision-making positions.

Based on these conclusions, we below present recommendations to HR professionals and change agents, leaders of university S&T and national and European policymakers.

6.1 RECOMMENDATIONS TO HR PROFESSIONALS AND CHANGE AGENTS

- Equality needs continued and active engagement by HR professionals and change agents. Statistical data shows that despite the high amount and content-related width of activities and achievements, progress in female participation in the science system remains slow. In order to seize the momentum of change, the strong dedication of HR professionals and change agents for gender equality and diversity management needs to be maintained and equal treatment promoted as an issue entailing gender equality and diversity.
- Strategy papers, GEP and DP and guidelines fostering inclusion and eliminating discrimination have to be designed, implemented; progress monitored and evaluated and concrete actions implemented to achieve institutional targets.
- In order to attract, recruit and retain qualified female researchers to STEM, transparency in recruitment and promotion processes has to be ensured, unconscious bias detected and tackled, leakages in the career pipeline identified and analysed and based thereon, effective measures fostered and expanded and new targeted measures developed.
- This has to start at the entry point of the scientific career path. Graduate figures show that only about one-third of bachelor and master graduates in STEM are women. Yet numbers drop at PhD level. Consequently, measures have to target early-career stages of bachelor and master studies in order to get more female PhD graduates. Furthermore, more women in elevated stages of the scientific career provide role models, which in turn potentially influence study decisions by girls or female students at the beginning of their career.
- It is necessary that HR professionals, change agents and universities liaise with different societal players such as schools, policymakers and governments to set up measures and programmes to inspire more girls to study STEM.
- Once women have entered an academic career and are motivated to take on leadership roles in academia, HR professionals and change agents have to support them in gaining visibility at the top-level of university management. High visibility is one of the most effective drivers of women to university leadership positions and is crucial in order to ensure gender balance at all decision-making levels and advisory boards.
- In addition to vertical, target-group specific measures, the development and implementation of comprehensive horizontal measures helps achieving better work-life balance, removing barriers to access and enabling people to thrive within in science.
- Equal participation in science entails monitoring of targeted measures across a broad field of diversity dimensions such as ethnicity, physical and mental ability, age, gender identity and sexual orientation. Efforts should be targeted towards equal access to and equal career progression opportunities within the science system regardless of background.
- Regarding diversity, there are numerous activities in place. In order to evaluate the implementation of these measures, it will be necessary to collect more structured data on the diversity of university members. This is already the case in some European countries such as the UK and thus best practice examples for guidance exist.
- The diversity activities analysed target a broad population of diverse people. Our evaluation shows that target dimensions are not necessarily fully congruent with implemented diversity activities. Therefore, we recommend that the development and prioritisation of initiatives is in line with pre-defined objectives.
- In order to evaluate the success of equality initiatives, evaluators have to consider the different subject areas of the university separately. There are many side effects and different framework conditions impeding a clear cause-effect-analysis.

- Collaboration, exchange and best practice sharing among HR professionals will stimulate discussion and open up new routes to achieve equality goals at universities of S&T.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS TO UNIVERSITY LEADERS

- Equality is already on the leadership agenda of universities of S&T. Rectorates, deanships and boards take responsibility for gender equality and diversity. Yet this paper has shown that equality is both leadership responsibility and simultaneously concerns all university members. Thus, university leaders are encouraged to lead by example and be explicit and visible on gender equality and diversity. Moreover, change has to take account of culture and structure; thus, strategic and overarching measures are necessary to promote a university culture of inclusion for everyone across the entire organisation.
- The survey results illustrate that organisational anchoring is most commonly adopted. Yet leadership responsibility for diversity and gender equality does not automatically determine the existence of an organisational unit whereby participants in 2014 and 2018 consider such special organisational units important to promote change in the entire institution.
- We recommend that a simultaneous top-down and bottom-up approach is adopted. The strategic and organisational structure underpinned with sufficient resources as well as anchoring of gender equality and diversity at the leadership level is important and has to be continued. Yet lack of awareness of equality issues is a main barrier when setting up activities. To reach broad acceptance of (in-) equality issues, to create and seize momentum for institutional inclusion and diversity, we encourage university leaders to address all university members and counteract internal resistance through dedicated sensitisation and awareness-raising measures.
- A leadership culture in which equal opportunities are viewed as a sign of quality has to be developed and appropriate behaviour rewarded.
- Universities should remove any (hidden) inequalities in earning powers for female employees and assure gender mainstreaming into top positions.

6.3 RECOMMENDATIONS TO NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN POLICYMAKERS

- This white paper has shown that equality efforts at universities of S&T encompass targets and measures fostering diversity and – to a greater extent – gender equality. The findings illustrate the sustainable positive impact (e.g. in Scotland and Germany) of regional, national and EU level regulations, incentive systems and research funding programmes and thus the significance of a favourable political and legal environment in order to promote equality. Therefore, we encourage national governments to design and implement policies promoting equality in research, higher education and universities.
- Moreover, it will be beneficial if national and European funding institutions acknowledge and support a broader perspective on equal opportunities beyond the gender equality perspective. Diversity-specific funding instruments and projects will foster a strategic perspective on diversity through the implementation of DP at universities.
- Efforts in promoting equality in research have to be reinforced through the ERA and strengthening the gender and diversity dimensions in research content.
- Greater momentum for the realisation of equal treatment and inclusion for all and the elimination of bias at universities of S&T will require instruments including incentive as well as sanction mechanisms.

ANNEX A: LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
EC	European Commission
FP	EU Framework Programme for Research & Innovation
HR	Human Resources
BME	Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Chalmers	Chalmers University of Technology
DP	Diversity Plan
TU Delft	Delft University of Technology
EIA	Equality Impact Assessment
EPFL	<i>Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne</i>
ERA	European Research Area
ERC	European Research Council
FFRL	Family Friendly Research Leave
GAP	Gender Action Plan
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
TU Graz	Graz University of Technology
INSA Lyon	<i>Institut National des Sciences Appliquées Lyon</i>
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology
KTH	KTH Royal Institute of Technology
LUH	<i>Leibniz Universität Hannover</i>
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
PoliMi	<i>Politecnico di Milano</i>
PoliTo	<i>Politecnico di Torino</i>
PUT	Poznan University of Technology
RTU	Riga Technical University
RWTH	RWTH Aachen University
S&T	Science and Technology
TalTech	Tallinn University of Technology
TU Berlin	<i>Technische Universität Berlin</i>
TU Braunschweig	<i>Technische Universität Braunschweig</i>
TU Darmstadt	<i>Technische Universität Darmstadt</i>
TU Wien	<i>Technische Universität Wien</i>
UCD	University College Dublin
UPC	<i>Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya</i>
UPM	Technical University of Madrid
UPV	<i>Universitat Politècnica de València</i>
Strathclyde	University of Strathclyde
WUT	Warsaw University of Technology
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths
UN SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

ANNEX B: BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Charta der Vielfalt e.V. (2019): Diversity Management. Retrieved from: <https://www.charta-der-vielfalt.de/en/understanding-diversity/diversity-management/> [Accessed: 25/04/2019].
- Deutsche Forschungsgesellschaft (2019): Excellence Strategy. Retrieved from: https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/excellence_strategy/index.html [Accessed: 16/04/2019].
- European Commission (2015): The European Union explained: Enlargement. Retrieved from: https://europa.eu/european-union/topics/enlargement_en [Accessed: 11/04/2019].
- European Commission (2017): Interim Evaluation of Horizon 2020. Retrieved from: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/fad8c173-7e42-11e7-b5c6-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-77918455> [Accessed: 23/03/2019].
- European Commission (2018): HORIZON 2020 full swing. Three years on. Key facts and figures 2014-2016. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/Horizon_2020/sites/Horizon_2020/files/h2020_threeyearson_a4_horizontal_2018_web.pdf [Accessed: 21/03/2019].
- European Commission (2019): She Figures 2018. Retrieved from: <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9540ffa1-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> [Accessed: 15/03/2019].
- European Institute for Gender Equality (2019): Concepts and definitions. Retrieved from: https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/concepts-and-definitions#letter_g [Accessed: 25/04/2019].
- European Research Council (2018): Annual Report on the ERC activities and achievements in 2017. Retrieved from: https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/erc_annual_report_2017.pdf [Accessed: 21/03/2018].
- Groutsis, Dimitria, Ng, Eddy S., and Ozturk, Mustafa Bilgehan (2014) Cross-cultural and diversity management intersections: lessons for attracting and retaining international assignees. In: Özbilgin, Mustafa F., Groutsis, Dimitria, and Harvey, William S., (eds.) International Human Resource Management. Cambridge University Press, New York, NY, USA, pp. 23-46.
- Horvat, M. (2015): Results of the CESAER Gender Equality Survey 2014, Final report 2015. Retrieved from: <https://www.cesaer.org/content/statements-and-publications/2015/cesaer-gender-equality-oct15-incl-annexes.pdf> [Accessed: 25/04/2019].
- Ranga, M., Gupta, N, and Etkowitz, H. (2012): Gender Effects in Research Funding, A review of the scientific discussion on the gender-specific aspects of the evaluation of funding proposals and the awarding of funding. Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. Retrieved from: https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/dfg_im_profil/geschaeftsstelle/publikationen/studien/studie_gender_effects.pdf [Accessed: 24/04/2019].
- Wallon, G., Bendiscioli, S. and Garfinkel, M.S. (2015): Exploring quotas in academia. EMBO. Retrieved from: http://www.embo.org/documents/science_policy/exploring_quotas.pdf [Accessed: 15/03/2019].

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ANNEX E: EQUALITY SURVEY 2018 QUESTIONNAIRE

This is the second Equality Survey to implement [CESAER's commitments](#) to the realisation of the [European Research Area](#). It has been elaborated by the CESAER Task Force Human Resources and builds upon our [Gender Equality Survey 2014](#). The survey has been adjusted along the feedback received. Importantly, it covers both diversity and gender equality. That is why we added new sections to the questionnaire enabling us to determine how our Members deal with variables, such as culture, age, religion or physical ability. Gender - as a diversity dimension - is still queried separately in order to safeguard comparability with the data from 2014. The systematic collection of data will enable our Members to monitor their activities and to benchmark their progress as well as to assess the effectiveness and efficiency, the benefits and impacts of their plans and activities over time. We will publish the findings in early 2019 and present them during the next General Assembly in autumn 2019 as learning from exchange of information and experiences – good and bad ones - is useful. We may use the results of this survey to prepare for a Declaration on Equality by the end of 2019. The structure of the questionnaire is as follows:

1. **IDENTIFICATION OF RESPONDENT**
 - 1.1. This part is obligatory in order to identify the respondent.
2. **STRUCTURES AND MEASURES SUPPORTING DIVERSITY**
 - 2.1. The completion of this part is voluntary and linked to the existence of a diversity policy at your institution.
3. **STRUCTURES AND MEASURES SUPPORTING GENDER EQUALITY**
 - 3.1. We kindly invite you to complete this part in any case as it will provide for qualitative information completing the quantitative data received from part 5.
4. **STRATEGIES, BEST PRACTICES, BARRIERS, TOOLS AND RESOURCES**
 - 4.1. We kindly invite you to complete this part in any case as it will provide for strategic information as well as provide for the dissemination of tools and resources amongst our Members.
5. **QUANTITATIVE DATA 2017**
 - 5.1. Completion of this part 5 is essential as it is fully aligned with the data collection from 2014 and will provide not only for updated information, but also allow for the identification of trends.

The questionnaire takes approximately 30 minutes to complete.

In case of questions or enquiries regarding this questionnaire, please do not hesitate to contact the RWTH Aachen University Integration Team - Human Resources, Gender and Diversity Management (IGaD) via genderanddiversity@rwth-aachen.de or +49 241 80 90627 (IGaD Office). We kindly invite you to complete the online questionnaire until the 2nd of July 2018 24:00 CET.

PART I: IDENTIFICATION OF RESPONDENT

Please note, that we only look for qualitative and quantitative data aggregated at the level of the institution as a whole. That is why we have sent the invitation to complete this CESAER Equality Survey 2018 to the Rector or equivalent of your institution.

This part 1 contains two short questions.

1. Select your university.
2. Contact person:
 - First name:
 - Last name:
 - Function:
 - Email:
 - Phone:

PART II: STRUCTURES AND MEASURES SUPPORTING DIVERSITY

Diversity management strives to create a fair and constructive working environment for all members of your university, regardless of their sex, age, origin, skin color, religion, disability or sexual orientation.

In this part of the questionnaire we would like to know how diversity management is embedded within your institution. It will ask about organisational structures, diversity and/or gender equality plans and activities you might have in place.

This section includes five questions.

1. How is diversity embedded within your university? (multiple answers possible)
 - The Rector, equivalent or member of the Board is responsible for diversity.
 - The Deans/faculties are responsible for diversity.
 - There is a commission dealing with diversity.
 - There is a special organisational unit dealing with diversity.
 - There are several organisational units dealing with one diversity dimension respectively (e.g. office for employees with disabilities, equal opportunities office)
 - Diversity is dealt with among other issues in a unit with broader responsibilities.
 - There is an external advisory group.
 - No special organisational unit is established in my university, but a single person is:
 - dealing with diversity only;
 - dealing with diversity among other responsibilities.
 - There is no special department nor person responsible for diversity.

2. Does your university have a Diversity Plan (or equivalent)?⁸
- Yes, there is a Diversity Plan⁹.
 - Yes, there is a Gender Plan and a Diversity Plan.
 - If yes, please insert the web link(s) to your plans, strategies or equivalent or send a PDF file to genderanddiversity@rwth-aachen.de.
 - No, there is no standalone Diversity Plan, but (multiple answers possible):
 - diversity is an integrated part of the University Strategy.
 - we plan to develop a Diversity Plan.
 - we plan to develop a Gender and Diversity Plan.
3. Which of the following target dimensions were most important at your institution in 2016 and 2017? Please choose up to 7 answers.
- change academic and organisational culture
 - change organisational structures and processes
 - assure non-discrimination
 - promote inclusiveness
 - provide accessibility for various groups (study and working conditions)
 - reduce underrepresentation
 - establish research and teaching that incorporate diversity
 - visualise diversity in your institution
 - raise awareness and develop diversity competences
 - facilitate work-life balance, including family-friendliness
 - strengthen internationalisation
 - strengthen gender equality
 - strengthen age diversity
 - foster inclusion of confessional diversity
 - others, please specify. (maximally 100 characters with spacing)
4. Which of the following diversity activities were in place at your university in 2016 and 2017? (multiple answers possible)
- draw up concepts or strategy papers
 - develop guidelines for administrative action
 - set quota regulation or targeted figures
 - monitor diversity
 - public relations, i.e. publish newsletter, publications and undertake campaigns
 - organise events on diversity
 - develop diversity competence at your university (e.g. trainings or workshops)
 - offer training programmes for students and lecturers
 - apply equal opportunities in recruiting processes (e.g. anonymous application, diversity-sensitive appointment processes)
 - provide funding for diversity-related research
 - advise on diversity aspects in teaching and research
 - offer specific consulting services and appeal system (e.g. family service, non-discrimination complaint point)
 - apply specific measures and programmes for the promotion of individuals from under-represented groups (e.g. scholarships)
 - offer structural career programmes and mentoring for individuals from under-represented groups
 - provide structural support (e.g. accessible education, home office or e-learning)
 - others, please specify. (maximally 100 characters with spacing)
5. Does your organisation evaluate the implementation of the Diversity Plan?
- Yes
 - No
- If yes, please explain how.

PART III: STRUCTURES AND MEASURES SUPPORTING GENDER EQUALITY

Gender equality management strives to establish equal treatment and equal opportunities for all members of your university. Due to the existing underrepresentation of women in research, it specifically aims at increasing the proportion of women at various organisation and career levels. In this part of the questionnaire we would like to know how gender equality is embedded within your institution. It will ask about organisational structures, strategies and activities you might have in place. This part includes five questions.

⁸ The term Diversity Plan also includes action plans, strategies or equivalent. The existence of a target definition of equal opportunities and a written/adopted strategy is determining.

⁹ The Diversity Plan may include gender as one diversity dimension

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6. How is gender equality embedded within your university? (multiple answers possible)
- The Rector, equivalent or a member of the Board is responsible for gender equality.
 - The Deans/faculties are responsible for the gender equality.
 - There is a commission focusing on gender equality.
 - There is a special organisational unit focusing on gender equality.
 - Gender equality is dealt with among other issues in a unit with broader responsibilities.
 - There is an external advisory group.
 - No special organisational unit is established in my university, but a single person is:
 - dealing with gender equality only;
 - dealing with gender equality among other responsibilities;
 - No special department or person is responsible for gender equality.
7. Does your university have a Gender Equality Plan (or equivalent)?¹⁰
- Yes, there is a Gender Equality Plan.
 - Yes, there is a Gender Plan and a Diversity Plan.
 - If yes, please insert the web link (-s) to your plans, strategies or equivalent or send a PDF file to genderanddiversity@rwth-aachen.de.
 - No, there is no standalone Gender Equality Plan, but (multiple answers possible):
 - gender equality is an integrated part of the University Strategy.
 - we plan to develop a Gender Equality Plan.
 - we plan to develop a Gender and Diversity Plan.
8. Which of the following target dimensions are most important at your institution? Please choose up to 7 answers.
- change academic and organisational culture
 - change organisational structures and processes
 - protect from sexual abuse
 - assure non-discrimination
 - promote inclusiveness
 - reduce underrepresentation
 - increase the proportion of women in the higher ranks of the academic hierarchy
 - establish research and teaching that incorporate gender equality
 - visualise gender equality in your organisation
 - raise awareness
 - others, please specify. (maximally 100 characters with spacing)
9. Which of the following gender equality activities were in place at your university in 2016 and 2017? (Multiple answers possible)
- draw up concepts or strategy papers
 - develop guidelines for administrative action
 - set quota regulation or targeted figures
 - monitor gender equality
 - public relations, i.e. publish newsletter, publications and undertake campaigns
 - organise events on gender equality
 - develop gender competence at your university (e.g. trainings or workshops)
 - offer training programmes for students and lecturers
 - apply equal opportunities in recruiting processes (e.g. anonymous application, diversity-sensitive appointment processes)
 - offer advice on gender-neutral language in job descriptions
 - provide funding for gender-related research
 - advise on the gender aspects of research proposals
 - offer specific consulting services and appeal system for female students or researchers (e.g. family service, non-discrimination complaint point)
 - apply specific measures for attracting female students to engineering studies
 - apply specific measures and programmes to promote female talents (e.g. scholarships)
 - offer structural career programmes and mentoring for women
 - provide structural support (e.g. home office or e-learning)
 - offer networking opportunities for female researchers
 - set quota regulations or targeted figures (e.g. to increase the proportion of women in the higher ranks of the academic hierarchy)
 - set quotas to ensure a gender equal composition in your organisation's committees
 - others, please specify. (maximally 100 characters with spacing)
10. Does your organisation evaluate the implementation of a Gender Equality Plan?
- Yes
 - No
- If yes, please specify how.
-

¹⁰ The term Gender Equality Plan includes action plans, strategies or equivalent. The existence of a target definition of equal opportunities and a written/adopted strategy is determining.

20. Scientific staff (reference date: 31 Dec 2017) We follow the European grading system. For explanation, please see pages 196-203 at https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/she_figures_2015-final.pdf Total number of people in grade A (Full professors or equivalent as the highest post at which research is normally conducted):
- Total number of women in grade A:
- 20.1.
- Total number of people in grade B (*associate professors or equivalent*):
 - Total number of women in grade B:
- 20.2.
- Total number of people in grade C (*assistant professors or equivalent*):
 - Total number of women in grade C:
- 20.3.
- Total number of people in grade D or other scientific staff:
 - Total number of women in grade D or other scientific staff:
21. Students, including Bachelor, Master and PhD students (reference year: 2017)
- Total number of students:
 - Total number of female students:
- Graduates (reference date: 31 Dec 2017)
- 21.1.
- Total number of bachelor graduates:
 - Total number of female bachelor graduates:
- 21.2.
- Total number of master graduates:
 - Total number of female master graduates:
- 21.3.
- Total number of doctoral/PhD graduates:
 - Total number of female doctoral/PhD graduates:
22. ERC Grants (reference date: 31 Dec 2017; awarded in 2017 and earlier)
- 22.1.
- Total number of ERC starting grantees:
 - Total number of female ERC starting grantees:
- 22.2.
- Total number of ERC consolidator grantees:
 - Total number of female ERC consolidator grantees:
- 22.3.
- Total number of ERC advanced grantees:
 - Total number of female ERC advanced grantees:
23. Marie Skłodowska Curie fellows (reference date: 31 Dec 2017)
- 23.1.
- Total number of outgoing Marie Skłodowska Curie fellows:
 - Total number of female outgoing Marie Skłodowska Curie fellows:
- 23.2.
- Total number of incoming Marie Skłodowska Curie fellows:
 - Total number of female incoming Marie Skłodowska Curie fellows:
24. Horizon 2020 project coordinators: (reference date: 31 Dec 2017)
- 24.1. T
- Total number of Horizon 2020 project coordinators:
 - Total number of female Horizon 2020 project coordinators:
25. Do you have information or data about the diversity amongst the members of your university (e.g.: age structure of the academic staff or number of the students with disabilities)?
- Yes No
- If yes, please specify. (maximally 500 characters with spacing)
 If yes, please send your information or data via email to genderanddiversity@rwth-aachen.de

ANNEX F: LIST OF BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLES

UNIVERSITY	BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLES (UP TO THREE INITIATIVES)
Aalto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Embedding the equality/diversity work as part of the quality work of Aalto University - Accessibility specialist working at the university - Reporting of the misconduct or harassment can be done in various levels, both at the department, or at the University level
BME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Girls' Day (Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Informatics) and Equality and Career Day by Directorate of Student Services
Chalmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender workshops for key persons - Integrate gender perspective in templates for all decisions - Workshops to combat master suppression techniques
EFPL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruitment of professors through tenure track system & hiring practices implemented by some deans to require at least one outstanding female candidate in short list - Extensive on campus child care structures - Representation of women in top position, among which two female deans
ETH Zurich	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect Campaign - Annual Gender Monitoring for entire institution and each Department
UGent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender balanced board of governors (best in Europe 50/50 see databank EIGE also) - HeForShe campaign - Coaching & diversity for students
INSA Lyon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many initiatives oriented towards French schools to encourage girls to apply to INSA. For 3 years, women represent 43% of two years students, but only 35% among graduates.
KIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender Consulting / Gender Monitoring (GEP, annual reports) - Structural support and services with regard to gender equality issues - Promotion of female researchers: Development Program for High Potentials
KTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The GOFL-programme: Gender Equality, Organization and Change Management is a leadership program for women in all areas of KTH - research and administration. - KTH Equality Office was established in 2017 and is part of the general aim to increase the organisation and structure of equality and diversity work at KTH. Several internal actors have focused on equality and diversity for the past several years specifically, including FFA, JMLA, the Student union and the different unions.
KU Leuven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KU Leuven uses gender vanguards in each evaluation and selection committee for academic staff to safeguard the gender sensitivity of evaluation and selection procedures. A more qualitative assessment where the number of publications no longer prevails and non-academic experiences (e.g. parental leave). - A mentoring-mentee programme was set up: a tool to enhance the recruitment of women at the SAS level in the longer term.
LUH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team-Mentoring for female PhDs - Niedersachsen Technikum for female students/pupils in STEM - Caroline-Herschel programme [guest professorship programme for female professors]

UNIVERSITY	BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLES (UP TO THREE INITIATIVES)
NTNU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy and action plan. Responsibility for an inclusive and diverse culture at work and throughout the organisation ultimately rests with NTNU's managers at all levels. - Diversity and organisational culture included in the policy and action plan. Gender and Diversity Budget 550 000 EUR each year. - Search committee, search for women before announcement of academic position. The challenge is to change the academic culture to include women in decision making at all levels in the organisation.
PoliMi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support to PhD student's childcare - Techcamp at Polimi: summer camps for high school female students to learn programming, robotics and other technologies - Work with associations to promote STEM studies in schools
PoliTo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Life-work and ageing conciliation service, Home care services for the elderly and disabled are provided. They are directly addressed to all staff (administrative and academic), their spouses and first-degree relatives - National and international networking - Survey on Quality of life at the workplace
PUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 'Girls to technical universities': every year a one-day event is organised at the campus, addressed to young women shortly before choosing the field of study (cooperation with schools) promoting tech. - 'International cafe' running on a regular basis to integrate Polish and international students also in non-academic activities. Each year an 'Intercultural week' is organised in cooperation with other Poznan Universities. - Library offer of technical equipment for visually impaired students.
RWTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mature, mandatory structures and strategies supporting equality and diversity e.g. Gender Triangle of Rectorate, IGaD and Gender Equality Officer; 30% Quota for personnel funding in the frame of the German Excellence Initiative, mandatory Gender Consulting for research proposals. - Diversity Days 2016/2018: university-wide event to raise diversity awareness and sensitivity; Diversity Days 2018: inclusion: people with disabilities and chronic diseases. - Proactive Sourcing of female professors - RWTH forumDiversity - Equal Treatment and Non-discrimination Round Table - Golden Rules for Family-Friendly Management
Strathclyde	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Family Friendly Research Leave: 3 months paid research leave for academic staff returning from a period of maternity/adoption/shared parental leave of 4 months or more. - Equally Safe in Higher Education: project which developed a toolkit to challenge gender-based violence across Scotland's university campuses. - University sponsorship of 15 women per year to take part in external women only leadership development programme (Aurora) and creation of network for participants.
TU Berlin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of new steering instruments (e.g. definition of new targets for the proportion of women, new process for Plans for the Promotion of Women). - Project "Joint Programmes", which promotes alternative career paths for women in academia.
TU Braunschweig	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mentoring for female postdoctoral candidates, a programme to increase the number of female scientists. - PROFessorin: a programme providing women an incentive to participate in decision-making positions. - 'Baby Bag', official hand-over: The president invites parents and their babies and hands over the Baby Bag
TU Darmstadt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active recruitment: guidelines and funds for active recruitment of female researchers. - Guest professorship for female researchers. Up to 4 female guest researchers are promoted for 1-2 semesters. This programme starts in autumn 2018. - Advisory board for Gender Equality. Directed by the vice president for research and consisting of internal and external members to advise the chair of the TU Darmstadt concerning its Gender Equality Action.

UNIVERSITY	BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLES (UP TO THREE INITIATIVES)
TU Delft	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TUD offers flexible working hours, the possibility to work part-time, partially paid parental leave, and an International Children's Centre on campus providing child care and an international primary school. - The Delft Technology Fellowship: offers high-profile, tenure-track positions to outstanding female academic researchers in research fields in which TUD is active. - DEWIS: the women's network of TUD for staff members who are interested in gender and diversity-conscious policy.
TU Graz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender & Diversity become a strategic project between 2012 and 2015: 1. raising awareness & communication, 2. Making university accessible for disabled persons 3. Gender budgeting was started. Afterwards the strategy 'IDuK' was created in order to introduce diversity into teaching and research. - Career positions for women
TU Wien	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professorships exclusively for women: From 2016 to 2018 there have been 2 full professorships and 2 junior professorships advertised for women only. - Target agreements with deans/faculties: all faculties have defined specific targets and there are a number of activities. - Monitoring system: a yearly report on 'men & women at TU Wien'.
UCD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of a mandatory Equality Impact Assessment Tool for all policy review and development. - Launch of a Gender Identity and Expression policy and guidelines which includes the re-assignment of gender-neutral bathrooms, simple process for name change without official documentation, provision of official transcripts in the person's preferred name and training of over 100 frontline staff on gender identity and expression Development of an Equality, Diversity and Inclusion policy and strategy.
UPC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparency in results (annual) and communication and diffusion of plans, actions and results. - Incorporate in the various work groups by strategic projects people from the different collective groups of the university: teachers, students and administration staff.
UPM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporate the gender perspective in the academic regulations, favouring the participation of women with equal opportunities than men, ensuring that the proportion of women in the Faculty is balanced, setting an example and models for female students. - Include the Gender perspective in teaching and research, via consideration in degrees curricula and course programs. - Raising the visibility of the Equality Plan amongst personnel (Faculty and Support services) & students to raise awareness.
UPV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training in gender perspective in research aimed at students of the Doctoral School - Observance of the principles of Social Responsibility and the gender dimension in their internal and external relations - Recognition of the right to gender identity and expression through a specific protocol
WUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equality and non-discrimination embedded in Strategy of the University - Participation in a promotional action 'Dziewczyny na politechniki' - Mentoring for female PhD students (at Faculty level)

ANNEX G: FUTURE STEPS TO INCREASE EQUALITY

UNIVERSITY	FUTURE STEPS
Aalto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equality/Diversity marketing campaign is planned to complete during autumn 2018 - Shaking up the Tech' girls' day is held of October 2018 (target group: high school female students) - New Equality/Diversity plan for 2019-2021 will be drafted during the end of 2018 and in the beginning of 2019 - The Chair of the Equality committee will be the Provost during the next period (2019-2021) - New guidelines and processes for dealing with harassment and inappropriate conduct cases, incl. reporting
BME	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internationalisation
Chalmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invest SEK 300 million in 10 years to achieve even gender distribution
EPFL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement equal opportunities action plan 2017-20 - Implicit bias awareness training - Measures to support dual career needs - Review of processes and implementation of information and awareness raising measures to prevent and deal effectively with occurrences of harassment or discrimination - Increase involvement of schools and departments
ETH Zurich	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More direct searches for talented young female scientists; youth academy with special focus on girls
UGent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quota
INSA Lyon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Train staff and students - Integrate gender and diversity into scientific research
KIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of target for proportion of female junior professors with Tenure Track - Creation of the next Gender Equality Plan and Definition of targets - Raising Gender awareness through holding of unconscious bias trainings and gender-sensitive personal development approach
KTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase structure and organisation of equality and diversity work at KTH - Increase awareness and knowledge both among students, employees - Create inclusive cultures - Create equal conditions and opportunities for all students and employees
KU Leuven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - KU Leuven will invest in active search committees in order to motivate excellent female candidates to apply - Gender vanguards will become Diversity vanguards in the selection and promotion committees and hence will enlarge their scope and play an important role to defeat all type of biases such as culture, race, and atypical career paths - Faculty programs will be set up to improve intercultural competences among students and staff - A more pro-active approach towards physical and digital
KUT	We have prepared Gender equality policy and are going to increase awareness on this

UNIVERSITY	FUTURE STEPS
LUH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise female quotas, more women in boards and committees - Human resource and organisational development - More female students in STEM
NTNU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The policy for gender equality and diversity must be integrated in all aspects of NTNU's activities and applies to all employees, regardless of position - Gender balance in recruitment to and in career development in top-level academic positions and managerial positions - Better integration of international employees - Improved gender balance in programmes of study - Equal opportunities for career development for employees in technical and administrative positions
Polimi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research fund for researchers coming back after maternity leave - Prepare PhD and postdoc female students to become role models for STEM and research through a story telling course
PoliTo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support actions for attracting female students - Support actions for Refugees - Support actions for international students and researchers - Monitoring of the needs of staff with disability
PUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue the pre-set policy
RWTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Foundation of a Work Group on Inclusion made up of different university players with relevant expertise e.g. University Board, Faculties, Operational Health Management; representatives of employees and students with disabilities with the objective to make RWTH Aachen a more inclusive university - Renewal and modification of the university-wide Diversity Action Plan - Strengthening established initiatives and structures - Establishing Gender Governance in decentral structures e.g. faculties
Strathclyde	See Equality Outcomes, Athena SWAN Action Plan and Gender Action Plan
TalTech	Tallinn University of Technology is currently developing a regulation to address the equality among university members
TU Berlin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvement of personnel selection procedures, esp. the appointment process (e.g. implementation of active sourcing or potential analysis technique) - Analysis and improvement of the participation of female scientists in research alliances - Analysis and improvement to support female entrepreneurship and female founders
TU Braunschweig	<p>The TU Braunschweig and the Department of Engineering set new targets of women's representation for 2025</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Giving precedence to female researchers taking up temporary professorships - Giving precedence to females awarding teaching assignments in Engineering
TU Darmstadt	The TU Darmstadt started an evaluation process of its Gender Equality Plan. The next steps to increase equality depend on the output of the evaluation. Diversity as a topic is getting more and more important. There will be actions related to that.
TU Delft	STEAM remain as a whole the areas with the lowest participation of women, in terms of horizontal segregation, i.e. quantitative presence of women among graduates, and in terms of vertical segregation, i.e. proportional participation of women in high-level positions. Designing and carrying out customised GEP at TUD, being embedded in the institution and effectively initiate change in formal and informal structures aiming at transforming the culture; touching both internal organisational issues.

UNIVERSITY	FUTURE STEPS
TU Graz	In order to foster diversity knowledge a special training for researchers and university teachers consisting of 6 modules (from basic gender knowledge to ethics) is being developed in cooperation with gender & diversity experts, some of them have a STEM background.
TU Wien	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Celebrating 100 years of women at TU Wien in 2019; number of events and activities are planned - Conducting the H2020 project GEECCO (see http://www.geecco-project.eu/home/)
UCD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support the UCD Schools to develop gender equality actions plans as part of their Athena SWAN award application - Workshop with leaders in the University to get commitment to the implementation and embedding of the EDI strategic action plan in their areas - Improve data collection in order to be in a position to have a clear picture of the diversity make-up of the University - Review the recruitment process to encourage applications from under-represented groups
UPC	We are working on the III Equality Plan (2016-2020). At the end of 2018 we will begin to work on the action plan for the years 2019 and 2020. Probably, some actions will be repeated but new actions will also emerge to achieve the expected objectives: women and decision-making, incorporation of the gender perspective in the teaching, the glass ceiling in teachers (women) and in the administration staff.
UPM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adapt UPM regulations: Teaching and Recruiting Evaluation commissions with a balanced composition of men and women - Consideration of maternal leave for evaluating teaching and research activities of Faculty - Family-conciliation measures
UPV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote gender mainstreaming in teaching and research - Reinforce the criteria that guarantee the conciliation of all the members of the university - Promote the adoption of equality measures in collaborating companies - Apply the principles of the 2030 Agenda in the routines of the university

ANNEX H: INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL PUSH- AND PULL-FACTORS

UNIVERSITY	INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL PUSH- AND PULL-FACTORS
Aalto	Tenure Track recruitment guidelines include guidelines for the recruitment committees to promote equality.
BME	Girls' Day
Chalmers	- The government's demand for gender mainstreaming.
EPFL	- ETH Domain gender strategy including a monitoring and annual reporting of figures and resources allocated which puts responsibility and accountability on top leadership. - Networks such as the EPFL WISH Foundation and the ETH Women professors forum where top female researchers are involved to promote equal opportunities. - Cooperation among equal opportunities offices and universities on a regional and national level to implement mentoring etc. - High visibility actions.
UGent	Quota imposed by law or decree are the only things that work.
INSA Lyon	- Actions of communication to show that the engineer job is not reserved to men. - Actions take place at INSA in the framework of 'INSA Journeys' but also directly at local and regional schools. - Permanent communication in social networks to valorise careers of women-engineers and female-entrepreneurs. - Valorisation through meetings, communications, seminars. - Participation to French High School conference network on equality and gender. - Connection with laboratories of social and human science.
KIT	- Excellence Initiative - Tenure-Track-Program - Program-oriented research evaluation
KTH	Structural: - Creating KTH Equality Office, creating the JMLA-group (consisting of leaders from each school focusing on equality and diversity). - Mainstreaming equality and diversity in all regular processes at KTH. Culture: - Changing a sexist street name. - Workshops and training sessions for both employees and students. - Building national networks.
KU Leuven	- Gender vanguards. - Installation of diversity teams in each faculty creating awareness by presenting statistical data on student diversity to faculties. - Guidelines for physical accessibility of building
LUH	- Support from the government and the ministry of science and culture Lower Saxony (e.g. Professorinnenprogramm, Geschlecht-Macht-Wissen). - <i>Niedersächsisches Hochschulgesetz</i> (NHG). - Internal financial support

UNIVERSITY	INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL PUSH- AND PULL-FACTORS
NTNU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long/term planning in recruitment at all levels from student to professor. - Focus on these issues at top level by Rectors team and the Directors. - Rector dialogue meeting twice a year with the Deans and Departments leaders about gender equality and diversity work. - Gender equality in the budget process is also important. - Mentoring programme and Qualifications scholarship for women in associate professor positions. - Career counselling for women researchers by head of Department.
Polimi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Official participation in and sponsorship of the Milano Pride and events discussing issues of diversity, inclusion, respect. - Participation to Inspiring Girls a project that brings women professionals to the schools to encourage girls to pursue any career without gender stereotypes.
PoliTo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal activities aimed at life-work and ageing conciliation services.
PUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 'Girls to technical universities': every year a one-day event is organised at the campus, addressed to young women shortly before choosing the field of study (cooperation with schools) promoting tech. - 'International cafe' running on a regular basis to integrate Polish and international students also in non-academic activities. - Each year an 'Intercultural week' is organised in cooperation with other Poznan Universities. - Library offer of technical equipment for visually impaired students.
RWTH	<p>Internal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender and Diversity Management has been defined as leadership task. - Strong commitment of the rectorate to gender equality and family friendliness. - Mature structures for Gender Governance and Diversity Management. - Active Change Agents in place. - Good cooperation between the Gender & Diversity key players. <p>External:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiatives by the German government: Excellence University, Female Professors Programme - Federal state programme of North-Rhine-Westphalia for Gender Equality
Strathclyde	<p>The University participates in regional and national networks which share best practice in equality and diversity in higher education. These are extremely valuable in developing potential equality and diversity strategies and in identifying opportunities for collaborative working across institutions and organisations to impact upon equality and diversity issues.</p>
TU Berlin	<p>Internal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support of the whole academic management board of the TU Berlin (president, vice-presidents). - Inclusion of gender equality experts in all processes and issues (gender equality as cross-cutting aspect). - Possibility to try out new things on a project base and to consolidate successful projects. <p>External:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DFG's Research-Oriented Standards on Gender Equality fostered a huge improvement in gender equality. - Implementation of gender equality as a research relevant topic (e.g. Horizon 2020).
TU Braunschweig	<p>External:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - German Research Foundation (DFG), Female Professors Programme (German Federal Ministry for Education and Research, BMBF). <p>Internal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The 'Gender and Family Working Group and Jour fixe' aims to anchor gender equality and a family friendly university as a cross-sectoral task, to increase coordination of these activities and to provide for synergy effects. (https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/chancengleichheit/gleichstellung/strukturen/aggleichstellung/index.html).

UNIVERSITY	INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL PUSH- AND PULL-FACTORS
TU Darmstadt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guideline for anti-discrimination the actions related to active recruitment of female researchers - Very close cooperation between central and decentral levels, e.g. all departments have Gender Equality Teams and Gender Equality Action Plans. - Gender Equality officers are included in all important strategies, processes, papers etc.
TU Delft	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agreements on gender diversity are made in the management contracts between the Executive Board and the deans. - Women are involved in recruitment and selection procedures, and at least one female candidate is nominated. - The establishment of a Delft Women in Science network. - The establishment of the Delft Technology Fellowship. - The establishment of a Dual Career Service. - The opening of an International Children's Centre Centre on the TU Delft campus.
TU Graz	<p>The 50% quota for women's representation according to the university act is a powerful requirement. Even though the quota cannot be fulfilled most of the time a lot of discussion and awareness-raising is happening. The above-mentioned career positions for women give highly qualified junior scientists with a PHD the chance to further deepen their scientific study. They are co-financed by the rectorate and have risen the number of women as assistant profs from 11,7% in 2012 to 30,2% in 2017.</p>
TU Wien	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legal framework in Austria (includes a quota for decision-making bodies and top management). - Installation of a Department for Gender Competence at TU Wien. - Installation of a Committee on Equal Treatment at TU Wien.
UCD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The appointment of a Vice-President for EDI that sits on the Senior Management Team of the University and chairs the EDI group has greatly supported the equality agenda. - The review of the Dignity and Respect policy and provision of a wide range of supports and options for local level resolution in an informal manner if possible. This also included the training of over 100 managers in managing bullying and harassment issues that may arise in their area.
UPM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calls for scholarships business-sponsored to support postgraduate enrolment & job transition for female graduates. - Inclusion in the academic offer a UPM degree of Specialist of Gender, Technology, and Leadership, financed by the Regional Government of Madrid. - Execution of Project STEM Talent Girl, to develop girls' talent and promote the scientific & technology vocations amongst teenage girls to continue their education in STEM programs, through mentors, technological workshops, and scholarships.
UPV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The state normative set developed by the regional government has allowed concrete measures and actions in the area of gender equality. The legal regulations have made the creation of the responsible organic structures for equality between women and men a reality. - It is the government of the university that leads the change through the adoption of equality policies, being the vice rector of social responsibility and cooperation who directs those policies.
WUT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equality and non-discrimination embedded in Strategy of the University. - Participation in a promotional action 'Dziewczyny na politechniki' http://www.dziewczynynapolitechniki.pl/english - Mentoring for female PhD students (at Faculty level).

ANNEX I: GENDER EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY PLANS AND STRATEGIES

UNIVERSITY	DIVERSITY PLANS	GENDER EQUALITY PLANS
Aalto University	<p>The Aalto University Equality Plan 2016-2018: https://www.aalto.fi/sites/g/files/flghsv161/files/2018-11/the_aalto_university_equality_plan_2016-2018_.pdf Non-discrimination and equality webpage: http://www.aalto.fi/en/about/reports_and_statistics/equality_and_diversity/ Equality webpage: https://www.aalto.fi/aalto-university/equality</p>	
EPFL		<p>Equal Opportunities Action Plan: https://equality.epfl.ch/files/content/sites/equality/files/PlanAction/EPFL_BureauEgalite_WEB_ENG.pdf Equality and careers: https://equality.epfl.ch/Equality</p>
ETH Zurich		<p>Gender Action Plan 2014: https://www.ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/associates/services/Anstellung-Arbeiten/chancengleichheit/Strategie_und_Zahlen/Gender%20Action%20Plan/ENG/Gender_Action_Plan_e_08_14.pdf Gender Action Plan webpage: https://www.ethz.ch/services/en/employment-and-work/working-environment/equal-opportunities/strategie-und-zahlen/gender-action-plan.html</p>
KTH		<p>Plan for Gender Mainstreaming: https://intra.kth.se/en/anstallning/pa-lika-villkor/jikth-jamstalldintegrering-pa-kth-1.771963</p>
KU Leuven	<p>Diversity Policy Plan 2014-2017: https://www.kuleuven.be/diversiteit/pdf/6566_BRO_BELEIDSPLAN_DIV_UK.pdf</p>	<p>Gender Action Plan 2014-2017: https://www.kuleuven.be/diversiteit/pdf/BRO_GENDERACTIE_def_ENG.pdf</p>
LUH	<p>Basic Principles Diversity Management: https://www.chancenvielfalt.uni-hannover.de/fileadmin/chancenvielfalt/pdf/DiversityGrundsaeetze_engl-1.pdf# Diversity Strategy: https://www.chancenvielfalt.uni-hannover.de/en/diversity-management/diversity-strategy/</p>	<p>Gender Action Plan Webpage (German): https://www.chancenvielfalt.uni-hannover.de/de/ueber-uns/beratung/publikationen-und-veroeffentlichungen/gleichstellungsplan-2016/ Gender Action Plan Report 2016 (German): https://www.chancenvielfalt.uni-hannover.de/fileadmin/chancenvielfalt/pdf/Gleichstellungsplan_LUH_2017.pdf</p>
NTNU	<p>Policy for Gender Equality and Diversity 2018-2021: https://innsida.ntnu.no/wiki/-/wiki/English/Policy+for+Gender+Equality+and+Diversity+2018-2021</p>	

UNIVERSITY	DIVERSITY PLANS	GENDER EQUALITY PLANS
RWTH		Gender Equality Plan 2017-2022 (German): http://www.rwth-aachen.de/global/show_document.asp?id=aaaaaaaaabadace Equal Opportunities Action Plan 2017-2020: http://www.rwth-aachen.de/global/show_document.asp?id=aaaaaaaaabaymnr&download=1 Gender and Diversity Webpage: https://www.rwth-aachen.de/cms/root/Die-RWTH/Profil/~eni/Gender-Diversity/?lid=1 FESTA handbook of organisational change: http://www.festa-europa.eu/sites/festa-europa.eu/files/The%20FESTA%20handbook%20of%20organizational%20change.pdf
Strathclyde		Gender Action Plan 2017: https://www.strath.ac.uk/media/ps/sees/equality/Gender_Action_Plan.pdf Athena SWAN Action Plan: not publicly available
TU Berlin		Equal Opportunities Concept 2016-2020: https://www.tu-berlin.de/fileadmin/a70100710_gleichstellung/Servicebox_Gleichstellungsdownload/Gleichstellungskonzept_TUBerlin.pdf
TU Braunschweig		Equal Opportunities Downloads & Links (German): https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/chancengleichheit/service
TU Darmstadt		Short version equality concept (German): https://www.tu-darmstadt.de/media/frauenbeauftragte/relaunch/pdf_10/zentrale_dokumente/Gleichstellungskonzept_der_TU_Darmstadt_Kurzfassung.pdf
TU Delft	Diversity & Inclusion Webpage: https://www.tudelft.nl/en/about-tu-delft/working-at-tu-delft/coming-to-the-netherlands-tu-delft/good-reasons-to-work-at-tu-delft/diversity-inclusion/	
TU Graz	Equal Opportunities Plan (German): https://www.tugraz.at/fileadmin/public/Studierende_und_Bedienstete/Satzung_und_Geschaefst_und_Geschaefstordnungen_der_TU_Graz/Satzungsteil_Gleichstellungsplan.pdf	Career Advancement Plan for Women (German): https://www.tugraz.at/fileadmin/public/Studierende_und_Bedienstete/Satzung_und_Geschaefst_und_Geschaefstordnungen_der_TU_Graz/Satzungsteil_Frauenfoerderungsplan.pdf
TU Wien	Equal Opportunitites Plan 2017: https://www.tuwien.at/fileadmin/Assets/tu-wien/TU_fuer_alle/AKG/Equal_Opportunities_Plan_2017_final.pdf Equal Opportunities Plan Webpage (German): https://www.tuwien.at/tu-wien/tuw-fuer-alle/arbeitskreis-fuer-gleichbehandlungsfragen/gleichstellung-und-gleichstellungsplan/	Career Advancement Plan for Women 2017: https://www.tuwien.at/fileadmin/Assets/tu-wien/TU_fuer_alle/AKG/Career_Advancement_Plan_for_Women_at_TU_Wien_2017.pdf Career Advancement for women Webpage (German): https://www.tuwien.at/tu-wien/tuw-fuer-alle/arbeitskreis-fuer-gleichbehandlungsfragen/frauenfoerderung-und-frauenfoerderungsplan/

UNIVERSITY	DIVERSITY PLANS	GENDER EQUALITY PLANS
UCD		Gender Equality Action Plan 2016-2019: http://www.ucd.ie/t4cms/UCD%20Gender%20Equality%20Action%20Plan%202016%202019.pdf
UPC	Equality Plan (Catalan): https://igualtat.upc.edu/ca/pla Equality Webpage (Catalan): https://igualtat.upc.edu/ca Inclusion Webpage (Catalan): https://inclusio.upc.edu/ca	Gender Equality Plan (Catalan): https://govern.upc.edu/ca/consell-de-govern/consell-de-govern/sessio-4-2016-de-consell-de-govern/12/aprovacio-del-iii-pla-digualtat-de-gener-de-la-upc/12-46-aprovacio-del-iii-pla-igualtat-gener-upc.pdf/@@display-file/visiblefile/
UPM		Equality Plan (Spanish): http://www.upm.es/sfs/Rectorado/Gerencia/Igualdad/plan%20de%20igualdad.pdf
UPV		Equality Plan 2017-2020 (Spanish, Valencian): https://riunet.upv.es/bitstream/handle/10251/97582/BOUPV%20108-5.pdf?sequence=5&isAllowed=y

ANNEX J: OTHER TOOLS OR RESOURCES

UNIVERSITY	TOOLS OR RESOURCES TO SHARE IN THE 'MEMBERS ONLY SECTION' OF THE FUTURE KNOWLEDGE BASE OF CESAER.
Aalto University	Key figures of 2018 and reports: https://www.aalto.fi/en/aalto-university/key-figures-of-2018-and-reports Non-discrimination and equality: https://www.aalto.fi/en/services/non-discrimination-and-equality
ETH Zurich	Respect Campaign and Code of Conduct: http://www.respekt.ethz.ch/en/
KIT	Gender Monitoring (German): https://www.peba.kit.edu/2303.php
KU Leuven	Gender Action Plan, Interim Report: https://www.kuleuven.be/diversiteit/pdf/KU%20Leuven%20Genderrapport_interim_FINAL_with%20lay%20out%20edit.pdf
LUH	Mission Statement: https://www.uni-hannover.de/fileadmin/luh/content/webredaktion/universitaet/ziele/leitbild_luh2013.pdf Equal Opportunities Office webpage: https://www.chancenvielfalt.uni-hannover.de/en/
NTNU	Action plan against sexual harassment: https://www.ntnu.no/documents/2007190/2007510/brosjyre-edu.pdf/4b7df915-5b04-4702-a6dd-7447e521bffd
Polimi	Polytechnic Equal Opportunities (POP): https://www.polimi.it/en/the-politecnico/university-projects/polytechnic-equal-opportunities-pop/
RWTH	Website Integration Team Human Resources, Gender and Diversity Management (IGaD): http://www.igad.rwth-aachen.de/cms/~evny/IGAD/lidx/1/ RWTH Golden Rules for Family-Friendly Management: http://www.igad.rwth-aachen.de/cms/IGAD/Diversity-Management/~evom/audit-familiengerechte-hochschule/?lidx=1 FESTA Gender-sensitive Design of Criteria and Recruitment, Appointment and Promotion Processes in Academia: http://www.festa-europa.eu/sites/festa-europa.eu/files/PRINT_Handbook_FESTA.pdf
Strathclyde	Equality Outcomes 2017-2021: https://www.strath.ac.uk/media/ps/sees/equality/Strathclyde_Equality_Outcomes_2017-2021_April_final.pdf Advance HE: https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/
TU Berlin	<i>Zielzahlenkonzept</i> - target figures concept (German): https://www.tu-berlin.de/fileadmin/a70100710_gleichstellung/Gleichstellungscontrolling/TUBerlin_Zielzahlenkonzept_final.pdf <i>Eckpunkte zur Erstellung, Evaluation und Fortschreibung der Frauenförderpläne</i> - new process for Plans for the Promotion of Women (German): https://www.tu-berlin.de/fileadmin/ref23/Frauenbeauf_GkME/Foerderplaene/Eckpunkte-Frauenfoerderplan-22-04-2015.pdf

UNIVERSITY	TOOLS OR RESOURCES TO SHARE IN THE 'MEMBERS ONLY SECTION' OF THE FUTURE KNOWLEDGE BASE OF CESAER.
TU Darmstadt	Franziska-Braun-Award (German): https://www.tu-darmstadt.de/gleichstellungsbeauftragte/gleichstellungsstrategie_2/fbp/index.de.jsp Against sexualised discrimination and assault: https://www.intern.tu-darmstadt.de/achtung/index.en.jsp
TU Graz	Key objectives and focus areas - diversity: https://www.tugraz.at/en/tu-graz/university/key-objectives-and-focus-areas/diversity/
TU Wien	Career Advancement Plan for Women 2015: https://www.tuwien.at/fileadmin/Assets/dienstleister/abteilung_genderkompetenz/gender_ressourcen/Frauenfoerderungsplan/Career_Advancement_Plan_for_Women_at_TU_Wien.pdf Gender Equality in Engineering through Communication and Commitment (GEECCO) Project: http://www.geecco-project.eu/home/
UPC	Program of teaching exemptions for intensifying research after maternity leave (Spanish): https://govern.upc.edu/ca/consell-de-govern/consell-de-govern/sessio-04-2018-del-consell-de-govern/aprovacio-del-programa-d2019exempcions-docents-per-a-la-intensificacio-en-la-recerca-despres-d2019un-permis-maternal/aprovacio-del-programa-d2019exempcions-docents-per-a-la-intensificacio-en-la-recerca-despres-d2019un-permis-maternal/@@display-file/visiblefile/
UPM	Equality Unit (Spanish): http://www.upm.es/UPM/PoliticasiGualdad Sexual harassment protocol (Spanish): http://www.upm.es/sfs/Rectorado/Gerencia/Igualdad/Documentos/Protocolo%20acoso%20sexual.pdf Brochure with the summary of Equality Plan (Spanish): http://www.upm.es/sfs/Rectorado/Gerencia/Igualdad/Documentos/folleto%20unidad%20de%20Igualdad.pdf Project STEM Talent Girl (English): https://talent-girl.com/en/ Call for Scholarships for Girls (Spanish): http://www.upm.es/sfs/Rectorado/Gerencia/Igualdad/Documentos/convenio%20convocatoria%20thales%20firmado%20por%20el%20rector.pdf
UPV	Statutes (Spanish, Valencian): http://www.upv.es/organizacion/la-institucion/estatutos-upv-es.html Code of Ethics (Spanish, Valencian): https://riunet.upv.es/bitstream/handle/10251/102862/BOUPV%20113-10.pdf?sequence=9&isAllowed=y Gender identity and expression guidelines (Spanish, Valencian): https://riunet.upv.es/bitstream/handle/10251/102862/BOUPV%20113-17.pdf?sequence=10&isAllowed=y Action plan for cases of sexual harassment, harassment on grounds of sex, sexual orientation, gender identity and expression (Spanish, Valencian): https://riunet.upv.es/bitstream/handle/10251/110962/BOUPV%20119_8_Protocol%20d%27actuaci%C3%B3%20en%20els%20sup%C3%B2sits%20d%27assetjament%20sexual.pdf?sequence=6&isAllowed=y

ANNEX K: DIVERSITY DATA BEST PRACTICE EXAMPLES

Strathclyde Student Equality Monitoring Report:

https://www.strath.ac.uk/media/ps/sees/equality/Strathclyde_Students_Monitoring_Report_2017_final.pdf

Strathclyde Equality Monitoring Report - Staff:

https://www.strath.ac.uk/media/ps/sees/equality/Strathclyde_Staff_Annual_Equality_Monitoring_Report_2017.pdf

University College Dublin Equality, Diversity and Inclusion, Annual Report 2016 – 2017:

http://www.ucd.ie/equality/t4media/UCD%20Equality%20Diversity%20Inclusion%20Annual%20Report%202016_17.pdf